

On approximation of lattice-valued functions using lattice integral transforms [☆]

Viec Bui Quoc ^a, Michal Holčapek ^{b, *}

^a Department of Mathematics, Can Tho University, Campus II, 3/2 Street, Ninhkieu District, Cantho City, Viet Nam

^b CE IT4Innovations – Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling, University of Ostrava, 30. dubna 22, Ostrava, 701 03, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lattice integral transform
Lattice fuzzy transform
Residuated lattice
Integral kernel
Sugeno-like fuzzy integral
Function approximation

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the approximation capabilities of lattice integral transforms and their compositions in reconstructing lattice-valued functions. By introducing an integral kernel Q on the function domain, we define the concept of a Q -inverse integral kernel, which generalizes the traditional inverse kernel defined as a transposed integral kernel. Leveraging these Q -inverses, we establish upper and lower bounds for a transformed version of the original function induced by the integral kernel Q . The quality of approximation is analyzed using a lattice-based modulus of continuity, specifically designed for functions valued in complete residuated lattices. Additionally, under specific conditions, we demonstrate that the approximation quality for extensional functions with respect to the kernel Q can be estimated through the integral of the square of Q , and in certain cases, these extensional functions can be perfectly reconstructed. The theoretical findings, illustrated through examples, provide a strong foundation for further theoretical advancement and practical applications.

1. Introduction

Integral transforms are mathematical operators that map a given function $f(x)$ to a new function $g(y)$ through an integral involving an integral kernel $K(x, y)$. This kernel establishes a relationship between the domains of $f(x)$ and $g(y)$, say, X and Y . Specifically, the transformed function $g(y)$ is obtained as:

$$g(y) = \int_a^b K(x, y) \cdot f(x) dx, \quad (1)$$

where $[a, b]$ defines the limits of integration. Prominent examples of integral transforms include the Fourier and Laplace transforms, which are widely applied to real and complex-valued functions. These transforms are powerful tools for addressing practical problems in diverse fields such as science and engineering. Common applications include solving ordinary and partial differential equations, signal and image processing, and spectral analysis of stochastic processes (see, e.g., [5,32,36]).

[☆] This work has been partially supported by the Czech Science Foundation through project No. 23-06280S and by the project “Research of Excellence on Digital Technologies and Wellbeing CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004583” which is co-financed by the European Union.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: bquiec@ctu.edu.vn (V.B. Quoc), Michal.Holcapek@osu.cz (M. Holčapek).

Fig. 1. Upper and lower approximations of a function that fails for compositions of lattice integral transforms.

In fuzzy set theory, we often work with functions whose values belong to an appropriate algebra of truth values, typically a residuated lattice or its specialized variants such as BL-algebras, MV-algebras, and IMTL-algebras (see, e.g., [4,11,26]). For such residuated lattice-valued functions, a specific class of “integral” transforms exists, referred to as *lattice-valued upper and lower fuzzy transforms* (or simply *lattice fuzzy transforms*). This concept was introduced by Perfilieva in [27] and has been further developed in various works [21–25,28,33]. The foundation of lattice fuzzy transforms lies in the *fuzzy partition* of the domain of the transformed functions. A fuzzy partition consists of a system of fuzzy subsets defined on the domain, generalizing the classical set-based partition in a natural and flexible manner (see, e.g., [27]). Using this partition, the direct and inverse upper and lower lattice fuzzy transforms are defined. The compositions of direct and inverse lattice fuzzy transforms enable the approximation of the original functions from both above and below. The quality of this approximation depends on the configuration of the fuzzy partition, which acts as a key tuning parameter. Notably, the lattice fuzzy transforms are closely connected to the operators of erosion and dilation in mathematical morphology on residuated lattices, as demonstrated in [31].

In [17], the authors showed that all types of lattice fuzzy transforms can be elegantly expressed as integral transforms, similarly to (1). In this formulation, the Lebesgue integral is replaced by Sugeno-like fuzzy integrals introduced in [9] and fuzzy relations serve as integral kernels that effectively substitute fuzzy partitions. Specifically, the fuzzy integrals employed to represent the direct and inverse lattice fuzzy transforms are defined using the least and greatest fuzzy measures on the corresponding measurable space (see, [17]). This insight initiated the development of a comprehensive theory of integral transforms for functions valued in complete residuated lattices (lattice integral transforms), extending the framework to incorporate more general fuzzy measures. Theoretical developments of lattice integral transforms, along with their applications in decision-making and image processing, are discussed in [14–16,18]. Among the natural questions, a prominent one concerns the approximation capabilities of lattice integral transforms. As mentioned earlier, compositions of lattice fuzzy transforms yield upper and lower approximations of the original functions. However, this property cannot be directly extended to integral lattice transforms, as can be seen in Fig. 1, leading to important questions about how their compositions approximate the original function and how to assess the quality of such approximations within the framework of complete residuated lattices. In this setting, traditional tools for analyzing real or complex-valued functions are not applicable, necessitating new methods tailored to the lattice structure.

This paper addresses these questions and builds upon the preliminary ideas presented in [18]. A critical element for successful reconstruction of original functions is the assumption that lattice integral transforms preserve constant functions. Therefore, we analyze the sufficient conditions required for this property to hold. Further, we introduce the concept of an inverse integral kernel, referred to as Q -inverse, for an integral kernel Q on the function domain, which is essential for reconstructing the original function through lattice integral transform compositions. In the main part of the paper, we extend Perfilieva’s results on upper and lower approximations, demonstrating that the composition of suitable lattice integral transforms bounds a transformed version of the original function either from below or above for an integral kernel Q . To measure how close the reconstructed and original functions are, in other words, to determine a quality of approximation, we define a lattice version of modulus of continuity for lattice-valued functions. We also show that, under the restriction $Y \subseteq X$ and certain conditions, the degree of closeness of the reconstructed and original functions, which are extensional with respect to the integral kernel Q on X that determines the inverse integral kernel, exceeds the value of the fuzzy integral of the square of the kernel Q . Note that in both cases, the smoothness of the original functions plays a crucial role, but it is assessed in different ways: through the modulus of continuity, which varies among functions, and through extensionality splitting the function space into two subspaces, namely, extensional and non-extensional functions. As a result, we show that, in addition to constant functions, extensional functions with respect to the fuzzy relation Q can be perfectly reconstructed under specific conditions involving integral kernels in a relation with fuzzy measures.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of fundamental concepts from algebras of truth values and fuzzy set theory that are utilized throughout the paper. Section 3 introduces key notions, including fuzzy measures and Sugeno-like fuzzy integrals for lattice-valued functions. In Section 4, lattice integral transforms are introduced and their properties are analyzed in the context of the objectives of the paper. Section 5 focuses on the definition of inverse integral kernels and their characteristics. The core contributions of the paper, concerning the approximation properties of lattice integral transforms and their compositions, are presented in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper with a summary of findings and future research directions.

2. Preliminaries

This part present the basic notions from algebras of truth values and fuzzy set theory that are used in the paper. For details, we refer to [4,26,20].

2.1. Algebras of truth values

In this paper, we suppose that the structure of truth values is a *complete linearly ordered residuated lattice*, i.e., an algebra $L = \langle L, \wedge, \vee, \otimes, \rightarrow, \perp, \top \rangle$ with four binary operations and two constants such that $\langle L, \wedge, \vee, \perp, \top \rangle$ is a complete linearly ordered lattice, where \perp is the least element and \top is the greatest element of L , $\langle L, \otimes, \top \rangle$ is a commutative monoid (i.e., \otimes is associative, commutative and the identity $a \otimes \top = a$ holds for any $a \in L$) and the adjointness property is satisfied, i.e.,

$$a \leq b \rightarrow c \quad \text{iff} \quad a \otimes b \leq c \tag{2}$$

holds for each $a, b, c \in L$, where \leq denotes the corresponding lattice ordering. The operation \otimes and \rightarrow are called the *multiplication* and *residuum*. A pair $\langle \otimes, \rightarrow \rangle$ of operations is called the *adjoint pair*.

Among the important complete residuated lattices belong the residuate lattices on the interval $[0, 1]$ defined by the left-continuous t-norm [4,12,19].

Example 2.1. Let T be a left-continuous t -norm. Then the algebra

$$L_T = \langle [0, 1], \min, \max, T, \rightarrow_T, 0, 1 \rangle,$$

where $a \rightarrow_T b = \bigvee \{c \in [0, 1] \mid T(a, c) \leq b\}$, is a complete linearly ordered residuated lattice. The most important examples of complete residuated lattices on $[0, 1]$ are obtained from the minimum, product, and Łukasiewicz t-norms:

$$T_G(a, b) = \min(a, b),$$

$$T_P(a, b) = a \cdot b,$$

$$T_L(a, b) = \max(a + b - 1, 0),$$

respectively. Their residua are as follows

$$a \rightarrow_G b = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a \leq b, \\ b, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$a \rightarrow_P b = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a \leq b, \\ \frac{b}{a}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$a \rightarrow_L b = \min(1, 1 - a + b).$$

The complete residuated lattices L_{T_G} , L_{T_P} and L_{T_L} on $[0, 1]$ are called the *Gödel algebra*, *product algebra*, and *Łukasiewicz algebra*, respectively.

On residuated lattices, we can introduce additional operations using the basic ones. An example of such operations are a unary operation of $\neg : L \rightarrow L$ called the *residuated negation*¹ and a binary operation $\leftrightarrow : L^2 \rightarrow L$ called the *biresiduum* given by

$$\neg a = a \rightarrow \perp, \tag{3}$$

$$a \leftrightarrow b = (a \rightarrow b) \wedge (b \rightarrow a), \tag{4}$$

for any $a, b \in L$. The following example presents the residuated negation for residuated lattices from Example 2.1.

Example 2.2. The residuated negations in the Łukasiewicz, Gödel, and product algebras are given as

$$\neg a = 1 - a, \tag{5}$$

(Łukasiewicz algebra)

$$\neg a = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a = 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } a > 0. \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

(Gödel and product algebra)

Note that the presented residuated negations are well-established in fuzzy logic (see, e.g. [12,26]).

¹ In the literature on residuated lattices, the residuated negation \neg in L is often simply called *negation*. However, since we will work with a more general notion of negation operations on L , we use the term “residuated negation” to emphasize that it is derived from the residuum operation.

A generalized concept of negation on a residuated lattice L , extending the usual residuated negation, may be introduced as follows (cf., [2]).

Definition 2.1. A unary operation $N : L \rightarrow L$ is called a *negation* on L if N is a non-increasing map such that $N(\perp) = \top$ and $N(\top) = \perp$.

In what follows, the residuated negation \neg is denoted by N_{res} . A negation N is said to be *involutive* if $N(N(a)) = a$ for all $a \in L$. For example, if $L = [0, 1]$, the function $N(a) = 1 - a$ defines an involutive negation on any residuated lattice from Example 2.1, although it is not, in general, a residuated negation.

The following example presents the biresiduum for residuated lattices of Example 2.1.

Example 2.3. The biresiduum in the Łukasiewicz, Gödel, and product algebras are given as

$$a \leftrightarrow b = 1 - |a - b|, \quad (\text{Łukasiewicz algebra}) \tag{7}$$

$$a \leftrightarrow b = \min(a, b), \quad (\text{Gödel algebra}) \tag{8}$$

$$a \leftrightarrow b = \min\left(\frac{a}{b}, \frac{b}{a}\right), \quad (\text{product algebra}) \tag{9}$$

where we put $\frac{a}{0} = 1$ for any $a \in [0, 1]$.

The following proposition presents the fundamental properties of the biresiduum utilized in this work (see, e.g., [4]).

Proposition 2.1. Let L be a residuated lattice, and let $a, b, c, d \in L$. Then it holds that

$$a \leftrightarrow a = \top, \tag{10}$$

$$a \leftrightarrow b = b \leftrightarrow a, \tag{11}$$

$$(a \leftrightarrow b) \otimes (b \leftrightarrow c) \leq a \leftrightarrow c, \tag{12}$$

$$(a \leftrightarrow b) \otimes (c \leftrightarrow d) \leq (a \otimes c) \leftrightarrow (b \otimes d), \tag{13}$$

$$(a \leftrightarrow b) \otimes (c \leftrightarrow d) \leq (a \rightarrow c) \leftrightarrow (b \rightarrow d), \tag{14}$$

$$(a \leftrightarrow b) \wedge (c \leftrightarrow d) \leq (a \wedge c) \leftrightarrow (b \wedge d), \tag{15}$$

$$(a \leftrightarrow b) \wedge (c \leftrightarrow d) \leq (a \vee c) \leftrightarrow (b \vee d). \tag{16}$$

Moreover, let L be a complete residuated lattice. Then the following items hold for arbitrary sets $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$, $\{b_i \mid i \in I\}$ of elements from L over an arbitrary set of indices I :

$$\bigwedge_{i \in I} (a_i \leftrightarrow b_i) \leq \left(\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i\right) \leftrightarrow \left(\bigwedge_{i \in I} b_i\right), \tag{17}$$

$$\bigwedge_{i \in I} (a_i \leftrightarrow b_i) \leq \left(\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i\right) \leftrightarrow \left(\bigvee_{i \in I} b_i\right). \tag{18}$$

2.2. Fuzzy sets

Let L be a complete linearly ordered residuated lattice, and let X be a non-empty universe of discourse. A function $A : X \rightarrow L$ is called an *L-fuzzy set* on X . In the sequel, we will simply refer to a *fuzzy set*, as the underlying residuated lattice L will always be clear from the context. The set of all fuzzy sets on X is denoted by $\mathcal{F}(X)$. A fuzzy set A on X is called *crisp* if $A = \top_Z$ for a certain $Z \subseteq X$, where \top_Z denotes the characteristic function of Z . Particularly, \emptyset denotes the empty fuzzy set on X , i.e., $\emptyset(x) = \perp$ for any $x \in X$. For the sake of better readability of the text, we do not distinguish between X and \top_X and similarly for Y, Z etc. The set of all crisp fuzzy sets (i.e., subsets) on X is denoted by $\mathcal{P}(X)$. A *constant fuzzy set* on X is denoted by \underline{a}_X , if $\underline{a}_X(x) = a$ for any $x \in X$. We use $\text{Supp}(A) = \{x \mid x \in X \ \& \ A(x) > \perp\}$ and $\text{Core}(A) = \{x \mid x \in X \ \& \ A(x) = \top\}$ to denote the *support* and the *core* of a fuzzy set A , respectively.

Let X, Y be non-empty universes. A fuzzy set $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ is called a (binary) *fuzzy relation*. The *transpose* of a fuzzy relation K is a fuzzy relation $K^T : Y \times X \rightarrow L$ given by $K^T(y, x) = K(x, y)$ for any $(y, x) \in Y \times X$. For $X = Y$, we say that K is a fuzzy relation on X . A fuzzy relation K on X is said to be *reflexive* if $K(x, x) = 1$ for any $x \in X$, *symmetric* if $K(x, y) = K(y, x)$ for any $x, y \in X$, and *transitive* if $K(x, y) \otimes K(y, z) \leq K(x, z)$ for any $x, y, z \in X$. A reflexive, symmetric, and transitive fuzzy relation K on X is called a *similarity* on X . For a fuzzy relation $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ and $x \in X$, a fuzzy set $K_x : Y \rightarrow L$ given as $K_x(y) = K(x, y)$ for $y \in Y$ is called an *x-projection* of K to Y . Similarly one can define a *y-projection* of K to X for $y \in Y$. A fuzzy relation K is said to be *normal*, whenever $\text{Core}(K) \neq \emptyset$, and *normal in the first coordinate*, whenever $\text{Core}(K_x) \neq \emptyset$ for any $x \in X$. Similarly one can define the *normality of K in the second coordinate*.

3. Fuzzy measure spaces and fuzzy integrals

In this section, we present basic notions from the theory of fuzzy measure spaces and fuzzy integrals for functions taking values in complete residuated lattices, which will be used later. For further reading, we refer the interested reader to [7,9,30,34,35].

3.1. Measurable spaces

In this paper, we consider algebras of sets as a background for fuzzy measure spaces.

Definition 3.1. Let X be a non-empty set. A subset \mathcal{F} of $\mathcal{P}(X)$ is an *algebra of sets on X* provided that

- (A1) $\emptyset, X \in \mathcal{F}$,
- (A2) if $A \in \mathcal{F}$, then $X \setminus A \in \mathcal{F}$,
- (A3) if $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$, then $A \cup B \in \mathcal{F}$.

A pair $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ is called a *measurable space* (on X) if \mathcal{F} is an algebra of sets on X . The sets from \mathcal{F} are called *\mathcal{F} -measurable*. As a simple consequence of (A2), (A3), and De Morgan’s law, we have that the intersection of finite number of \mathcal{F} -measurable sets is again \mathcal{F} -measurable. A useful tool how to introduce an algebra of sets on X is an algebra generated by a family of sets.

Definition 3.2. Let $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(X)$ be a non-empty family of sets. The smallest algebra on X containing \mathcal{G} is denoted by $\text{Alg}(\mathcal{G})$ and is called the *generated algebra by \mathcal{G}* .

Note that the intersection of algebras of sets on X is again an algebra of sets on X , hence, the smallest algebra on X containing \mathcal{G} always exists and its unique. Moreover, the generated algebra $\text{Alg}(\mathcal{G})$ can be simply constructed from the elements \mathcal{G} as the set which consists of all finite unions applied on the set of all finite intersections over the elements of \mathcal{G} and their complements. We now present some examples of algebras of sets.

Example 3.1. The sets $\{\emptyset, X\}$ and $\mathcal{P}(X)$ are the trivial examples of algebras of sets on X .

Example 3.2. Let L be a residuated lattice, and define $u : \mathcal{P}(L) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(L)$ as

$$u(X) = \{x \in L \mid \exists a \in X, a \leq x\} \tag{19}$$

for any $X \in \mathcal{P}(L)$. Obviously, $X \subseteq u(X)$. A set $X \in \mathcal{P}(L)$ such that $u(X) = X$ is called the *upper set* or *upset*. The set of all upsets in L is denoted by $\mathcal{U}(L)$. By definition, we have $\emptyset, X \in \mathcal{U}(L)$. Moreover, it can be shown that the intersection and union of any non-empty family of upper sets remain upper sets. Consequently, $\mathcal{U}(L)$ forms a topology on L , known as the Alexandrov topology. The algebra of upset sets is the generated algebra $\text{Alg}(\mathcal{U}(L))$. Note that the algebra of upset sets plays a fundamental role in the definition of measurable functions from X to L and their corresponding fuzzy integrals (see, e.g., [35] for $L = [0, \infty)$ or [17]).

3.2. Fuzzy measures and conjugate fuzzy measures

We introduce two types of set functions, namely, the fuzzy measure and conjugate fuzzy measure, with values in a complete residuated lattice. Note that the conjugate fuzzy measure to a given fuzzy measure was proposed in [7] to define a residuum-based integral (qualitative desintegral) for decreasing local evaluation scales.

Definition 3.3. A function $\mu : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow L$ is called a *fuzzy measure* on a measurable space $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ if

- (i) $\mu(\emptyset) = \perp$ and $\mu(X) = \top$,
- (ii) if $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A \subseteq B$, then $\mu(A) \leq \mu(B)$.

A triplet $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ is called a *fuzzy measure space* whenever $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ is a measurable space and μ is a fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$.

It should be noted that the term “fuzzy measure” was introduced by Sugeno in [30], but in the literature one can find the equivalent names for μ as a *capacity* or a *non-additive measure*. The following lemma shows an easy way to determine another fuzzy measure from a given fuzzy measure using a transformation function on $[0, 1]$.

Lemma 3.1. Let μ be a fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$, and let $\varphi : L \rightarrow L$ be a monotonically non-decreasing function with $\varphi(\perp) = \perp$ and $\varphi(\top) = \top$. Then the function $\mu_\varphi : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow L$ given by $\mu_\varphi(A) = \varphi(\mu(A))$ for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$ is a fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$.

Proof. Obvious. \square

Fig. 2. Functions φ (blue) and $\varphi^{c,N}$ (yellow) used to define the fuzzy measure and its N -conjugate fuzzy measure in Example 3.4. (For interpretation of the colors in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The following definition introduces the N -conjugate fuzzy measure, as originally presented in [15] (cf., [7,18]).

Definition 3.4. Let μ be a fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$, and let N be a negation on L . A function $\mu^{c,N} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow L$ given by $\mu^{c,N}(A) = N(\mu(X \setminus A))$ for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$ is called the N -conjugate fuzzy measure to μ .

Clearly, the N -conjugated fuzzy measure to μ is itself a fuzzy measure but constructed using two specific operations: negation and set complement.

Example 3.3. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ be a measurable space. For two fuzzy measures μ_1, μ_2 on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$, we say that μ_1 is less than or equal to μ_2 (denoted as $\mu_1 \leq \mu_2$) if $\mu_1(A) \leq \mu_2(A)$ for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$. The least and the highest fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ with respect to \leq is given by

$$\mu^\perp(A) = \begin{cases} \perp, & A \neq X, \\ \top, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu^\top(A) = \begin{cases} \perp, & A = \emptyset, \\ \top, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{20}$$

for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$, respectively.

Assume that L is a complete residuated lattice on $[0, 1]$. The following fuzzy measure belongs among the fundamental fuzzy measures.

Example 3.4. The relative fuzzy measure μ^r on a finite measurable space $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ with $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ is given as

$$\mu^r(A) = \frac{\#A}{n}, \tag{21}$$

for all $A \in \mathcal{F}$, where $\#A$ denote the number of elements in A . By Lemma 3.1, the relative fuzzy measure μ^r can be modified by a non-decreasing function φ with $\varphi(0) = 0$ and $\varphi(1) = 1$ to obtain a fuzzy measure μ_φ^r . An example (blue) of the function φ can be seen in Fig. 2. An N -conjugate fuzzy measure to μ_φ^r can be determined by the function $\varphi^{c,N}(x) = 1 - \varphi(1 - x)$ (yellow), where $N(a) = 1 - a$ for $a \in L$.

Another example of fuzzy measures and N -conjugate fuzzy measures can be found in [15].

3.3. Sugeno-like fuzzy integrals

The Sugeno-like fuzzy integral is a direct generalization of the Sugeno fuzzy integral introduced in [30] and further developed by numerous researchers (see, e.g., [35] for a review). It is designed for integrated functions evaluated in a complete residuated lattice, where the original meet (infimum) operation is replaced by a more general multiplication operation [7,8]. The definition of the fuzzy integral proposed in [7] aligns with the one given in [8] (see also [9]), provided that the multiplication is distributive over the infimum in the given residuated lattice. For convenience, we use f, g, h to denote residuated lattice-valued functions or, equivalently, fuzzy sets.

Definition 3.5. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ be a fuzzy measure space, and let $f : X \rightarrow L$. The \otimes -fuzzy integral of f on X is given by

$$\int^\otimes f \, d\mu = \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A} f(x) \right) \otimes \mu(A). \tag{22}$$

The next proposition recalls the basic properties of the \otimes -fuzzy integral (see, e.g., [8,9]). The relations and operations between functions are defined pointwise, e.g., $f \leq g$ if $f(x) \leq g(x)$ for any $x \in X$.

Proposition 3.2. Let $\underline{a}_X \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ be a constant function. For any $f, g \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ and $a \in L$, we have

- (i) $\int^\otimes f d\mu \leq \int^\otimes g d\mu$ if $f \leq g$,
- (ii) $\int^\otimes \underline{a}_X d\mu = a$,
- (iii) $a \otimes \int^\otimes f d\mu \leq \int^\otimes \underline{a}_X \otimes f d\mu$,
- (iv) $\int^\otimes \underline{a}_X \rightarrow f d\mu \leq a \rightarrow \int^\otimes f d\mu$,
- (v) $\int^\otimes \underline{a}_X \otimes \top_Z d\mu = a \otimes \mu(Z)$ for any $Z \in \mathcal{F}$.

4. Lattice integral transforms

In this section, we introduce two types of lattice integral transforms that generalize lattice fuzzy transforms. We also present selected properties of these transforms, including sufficient conditions for the preservation of constant functions - a property that is essential for achieving accurate approximations.

We begin with the concept of an integral kernel, defined as a fuzzy relation on the Cartesian product of X , the domain of the original functions, and Y , the domain of the transformed functions. The integral kernel extends the notion of a fuzzy partition of the function domain - a fundamental component in lattice fuzzy transforms [27], as demonstrated in [21]. The following definition possesses stronger properties than the original version presented in [17].

Definition 4.1. A fuzzy relation $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ is said to be an *integral kernel* provided that K is normal in both arguments, i.e., for any $x \in X$ there is $y \in Y$ such that $K(x, y) = \top$ and vice versa, for any $y \in Y$ there is $x \in X$ such that $K(x, y) = \top$.

Lattice integral transforms are designed to generalize the lower and upper lattice fuzzy transforms by utilizing the Sugeno-like fuzzy integral. In this framework, the integrand is the product of the transformed function and the integral kernel, where the product \star is one of the operations \otimes or \rightarrow . More broadly, a lattice integral transform is an operator that maps fuzzy sets from $\mathcal{F}(X)$ to fuzzy sets in $\mathcal{F}(Y)$, and was originally defined in [17] as follows.

Definition 4.2. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ be a fuzzy measure space, let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be an integral kernel, and let $\star \in \{\otimes, \rightarrow\}$. A map $F_{(K, \mu)}^\star : \mathcal{F}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(Y)$ defined by

$$F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f)(y) = \int^\otimes K(x, y) \star f(x) d\mu \tag{23}$$

is called a (K, μ, \star) -lattice integral transform.

The original definition of the (K, μ, \star) -lattice integral transform is slightly more general, as it requires only the semi-normality of the integral kernel in its second argument - meaning that for any $y \in Y$, there exists $x \in X$ such that $K(x, y) > \perp$. However, practical applications have demonstrated that semi-normality is too weak to produce satisfactory results. This observation motivated us to adopt the stronger assumption of normality for the integral kernel in both arguments. When the pair (K, μ) is known or does not need explicit mention, we simplify the notation and refer to it as a “ \star -lattice integral transform”, where \star highlights the specific operation used. For brevity, we may also use the term “lattice integral transform”.

Remark 4.1. As mentioned in Introduction, the direct and inverse lattice fuzzy transforms are special cases of lattice integral kernels. Specifically, assume that K is an integral kernel such that all y -projections K_y form a fuzzy partition of X , i.e., $\bigcup_{y \in Y} K_y = X$ and $\text{Core}(K_y) \cap \text{Core}(K_z) = \emptyset$ for any $y, z \in Y$ such that $y \neq z$. The direct upper and lower fuzzy transform is a (K, μ^\top, \otimes) - and (K, μ^\perp, \otimes) -lattice integral transform, respectively. The inverse upper and lower fuzzy transforms are defined similarly to the direct transforms but in the reverse order.

The following theorem outlines the fundamental properties of lattice integral transforms (for the proof, see [17]). We assume the existence of a fuzzy measure space $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ and an integral kernel $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$.

Proposition 4.1. For any $f, g \in \mathcal{F}(X)$, $\star = \{\otimes, \rightarrow\}$ and for any $a \in L$, we have

- (i) $F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f) \leq F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(g)$ if $f \leq g$,
- (ii) $F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f \cap g) \leq F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f) \wedge F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(g)$,
- (iii) $F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f) \vee F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(g) \leq F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f \cup g)$,
- (iv) $a \otimes F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f) \leq F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(\underline{a}_X \otimes f)$,
- (v) $F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(\underline{a}_X \rightarrow f) \leq a \rightarrow F_{(K, \mu)}^\star(f)$.

The following statement, describing the monotonicity properties of lattice integral transforms concerning the ordering of integral kernels and fuzzy measures, is an immediate consequence of their definition.

Theorem 4.2. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ be a measurable space, let μ, μ' be fuzzy measures on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$, and let $K, K' : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be integral kernels.

- (i) If $\mu \leq \mu'$, then $F_{(K, \mu)}^*(f) \leq F_{(K, \mu')}^*(f)$ for any $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$.
- (ii) If $K \leq K'$, then $F_{(K, \mu)}^*(f) \leq F_{(K', \mu)}^*(f)$ for any $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$.

The next theorem establishes the conditions under which a constant function (fuzzy set) \underline{a}_X is transformed into another constant function \underline{a}_Y , i.e., $F_{(K, \mu)}^*(\underline{a}_X) = \underline{a}_Y$. Here, K_y represents the y -projection of K onto X .

Theorem 4.3. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ be a fuzzy measure space, let K be an integral kernel, and let $a \in L$.

- (C1) If for any $y \in Y$ there exists $A_y \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A_y \subseteq \text{Core}(K_y)$ and $\mu(A_y) = \top$, then $F_{(K, \mu)}^\otimes(\underline{a}_X) = \underline{a}_Y$.
- (C2) If for any $y \in Y$ and for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$ with $A \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(K_y)$ it holds that $\mu(A) \leq a$, then $F_{(K, \mu)}^\rightarrow(\underline{a}_X) = \underline{a}_Y$.

Proof. See, [15]. \square

It is worth noting that the standard real-valued fuzzy transforms as well as lower and upper lattice fuzzy transforms preserve constant functions; therefore, it seems to be natural to assume that integral kernels and fuzzy measures as the parameters of the lattice integral transforms satisfy the conditions under which the constant functions are preserved. Moreover, the preservation of constant functions is a crucial condition for the successful reconstruction of original functions using lattice integral transforms, as demonstrated in [15] (see Example 6.1 later in this paper).

In what follows, we say that (K, μ) satisfies (C1) if the sufficient condition in (C1) holds for (K, μ) . Similarly, if the sufficient condition in (C2) holds for (K, μ) at every $a \in L$, we say that (K, μ) satisfies (C2). Thus, if (K, μ) satisfies (C1) (or (C2)), then $F_{(K, \mu)}^\otimes$ (or $F_{(K, \mu)}^\rightarrow$) preserves all constant functions on X . Observe that for any (K, μ) , the equality $F_{(K, \mu)}^\rightarrow(\underline{1}_X) = \underline{1}_Y$ holds trivially, since by Proposition 3.2(ii),

$$\int^\otimes (K(x, y) \rightarrow \underline{1}_X(x)) d\mu = \int^\otimes \underline{1}_X d\mu = \top.$$

Recall that $\mu^{c,N}$ denotes the N -conjugate fuzzy measure to μ . The next theorem shows a useful relation between the satisfaction of conditions (C1) and (C2) for μ and its N -conjugate fuzzy measure.

Theorem 4.4. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu \rangle$ be a fuzzy measure space, let K be an integral kernel.

- (i) If (K, μ) satisfies (C1), then $(K, \mu^{c,N})$ satisfies (C2).
- (ii) If (K, μ) satisfies (C2) and $\text{Core}(K_y) \in \mathcal{F}$ for any $y \in Y$, then $(K, \mu^{c,N})$ satisfies (C1).

Proof. (i) Assume that (K, μ) satisfies (C1), and let $y \in Y$ and $A \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(K_y)$. By the assumption there exists $A_y \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A_y \subseteq \text{Core}(K_y)$ and $\mu(A_y) = \top$. Hence, we find that $A_y \subseteq \text{Core}(K_y) \subseteq X \setminus A$, and thus $\top = \mu(A_y) \leq \mu(X \setminus A)$, which implies $\mu^{c,N}(A) = N(\mu(X \setminus A)) = N(\top) = \perp$. Therefore, (C2) is satisfied by $(K, \mu^{c,N})$.

(ii) Assume that (K, μ) satisfies (C2), let $y \in Y$ and put $A_y = \text{Core}(K_y) \in \mathcal{F}$. Then trivially $X \setminus A_y \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(K_y)$, and by the assumption, we have $\mu(X \setminus A_y) = \perp$ (recall that (C2) is satisfied for all $a \in L$, which is equivalent to (C2) is satisfied for $a = \perp$). Hence, we find that $\mu^{c,N}(A_y) = N(\mu(X \setminus A_y)) = N(\perp) = \top$. Therefore, $\mu^{c,N}$ satisfies (C1). \square

In the next example, we give a class of fuzzy measures that, together with a given integral kernel, satisfy (C1). In addition, we introduce the N -conjugate fuzzy measures to them, which satisfy (C2).

Example 4.2. Let $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ be a measurable space with $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, $L = [0, 1]$ and $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{P}(X)$. Let $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, and let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be an integral kernel. Put $a = \min\{\#\text{Core}(K_y) \mid y \in Y\}/n$. Obviously, $a > 0$, which follows from the normality of y -projections of K . Let $\varphi : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a non-decreasing function such that $\varphi(0) = 0$ and $\varphi(b) = 1$ for any $b \geq a$. Then μ_φ^r given in Example 3.4 is a fuzzy measure on $\langle X, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ such that (K, μ_φ^r) satisfies (C1). Indeed, for any $y \in Y$, it is sufficient to put $A_y = \text{Core}(K_y)$. Then $\mu_\varphi^r(A_y) = \varphi(\#A_y/n) = 1$, since $\#A_y/n \geq a$.

Let N be an arbitrary negation on L . As a consequence of Theorem 4.4(i), we get that $(K, \mu_\varphi^{r,c,N})$ satisfies (C2).

5. Inverse integral kernels

In this section, we introduce the concept of the inverse integral kernel, which facilitates the reconstruction of the original function from its transformed counterparts. We also examine its fundamental properties and investigate the role of the transpose integral kernel within the class of inverse integral kernels.

Let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be an integral kernel. Exploring fuzzy relations on $Y \times X$ that could be used to define the inversion of K leads to the concept of an inverse of K associated with an integral kernel Q on X . Incorporating Q into the definition allows for a more general framework for constructing inverse kernels.

Definition 5.1. Let $Q : X \times X \rightarrow L$ and $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be integral kernels. An integral kernel $K' : Y \times X \rightarrow L$ is said to be an Q -inverse of K if

$$Q(x, z) = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} K'(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y), \quad x, z \in X. \tag{24}$$

From the previous definition, we can see that Q is uniquely determined from K and K' by formula (24). In other words, if K' is a Q -inverse of K , then K' cannot be also a Q' -inverse of K for an integral kernel Q' different from Q . So, when we write that K' is a Q -inverse of K , we mean that Q is an integral kernel determined from K and K' by formula (24). Obviously, not each integral kernel K has its Q -inverse for each integral kernel Q , and also not all pairs of integral kernels K and K' lead to an integral kernel Q given by (24), i.e., Q is a fuzzy relation which is not normal in both arguments in general. As we have indicated, Q -inverses of K are different with respect to different Q . On the other hand, each integral kernel K has its transpose as a Q -inverse, where Q is determined by (24), as will be shown later. Interestingly, we can have different Q -inverses of K for the same Q as the following example shows, so, the Q -inverse is not defined uniquely.

Example 5.1. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$, and consider the Łukasiewicz algebra on $[0, 1]$. Assume that the integral kernels $K : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $K^T, K' : Y \times X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are expressed in matrix form as follows:

$$K = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.8 \\ 0.9 & 1 \\ 0.7 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad K^T = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.9 & 0.7 \\ 0.8 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad K' = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.9 & 0.7 \\ 0.7 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

We see that $K^T \neq K'$, since $K^T(y_2, x_1) = K^T_{21} = 0.8 \neq 0.7 = K'_{21} = K'(y_2, x_1)$. Introducing the matrix operation for a $p \times q$ -matrix K and a $q \times p$ -matrix M as

$$(K \rightarrow M)_{ik} = \min\{K_{jk} \rightarrow M_{ij} \mid j = 1, \dots, p\} \tag{25}$$

for any $i, k = 1, \dots, q$, we simply find that the integral kernel Q defined in (24) and expressed in the matrix form is

$$Q = K^T \rightarrow K = K' \rightarrow K = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.8 & 0.8 \\ 0.9 & 1 & 1 \\ 0.7 & 0.8 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, there are two different Q -inverses of K , namely, the transpose K^T and the integral kernel K' .

The following definition introduces the notion of compatibility between integral kernels, a useful concept first presented in [18].

Definition 5.2. Let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ and $K' : Y \times X \rightarrow L$ be integral kernels. An integral kernel $Q : X \times X \rightarrow L$ is said to be *compatible* with K and K' or also (K, K') -compatible provided that

$$Q(x, z) \otimes K'(y, z) \leq K(x, y) \tag{26}$$

holds for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$.

It is easy to see that if K' is a Q -inverse of K , then the integral kernel Q is (K, K') -compatible. Indeed, as a consequence of (24), we get $Q(x, z) \leq K'(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y)$ for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$, hence, (26) follows from adjointness property. In addition, if K has a Q -inverse, then there is also the *maximal Q -inverse* of K , where maximality is characterized with respect to the ordering of fuzzy sets (relations). Indeed, let us assume that K has a Q -inverse, and let $\{K_i \mid i \in I\}$ be the set of all Q -inverses of K . By the definition of the integral kernel, for any $y \in Y$, there are $x \in X$ and $i \in I$ such that $K_i(x, y) = \top$, which implies $(\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i)(x, y) = \bigvee_{i \in I} K_i(x, y) = \top$. Similarly we can prove that for any $x \in X$, there is $y \in Y$ such that $\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i(x, y) = \top$. Hence, $\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i$ is an integral kernel. Since Q is (K, K_i) -compatible for any $i \in I$, we get

$$Q(x, z) \otimes \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i\right)(y, z) = Q(x, z) \otimes \bigvee_{i \in I} K_i(y, z) \leq K(x, y)$$

for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Due to the adjointness property and the fact that the residuum is non-increasing in the first argument, we obtain

$$Q(x, z) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i \right) (y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y) \right) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} (K_i(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y)) = Q(x, z)$$

for any $x, z \in X$, which implies that $\bigcup_{i \in I} K_i$ is the Q -inverse of K .

In what follows, we use K^{-1} to denote an arbitrary Q -inverse of K . More precisely, if we use K^{-1} , then we mean one of the Q -inverses of K , including the maximal one. A natural question arises: can we determine an inverse of K from a given integral kernel Q ? The following proposition shows that for any integral kernels K and Q , one can construct integral kernels K' and Q^* such that $Q \leq Q^*$, and K' is a maximal Q^* -inverse of K . Recall that, by definition, Q^* is obtained from K and K' using formula (24).

Proposition 5.1. *Let $Q : X \times X \rightarrow L$, and let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be integral kernels. If the fuzzy relation $K' : Y \times X \rightarrow L$ given by*

$$K'(y, x) = \bigwedge_{u \in X} Q(u, x) \rightarrow K(u, y), \quad x \in X, y \in Y, \tag{27}$$

is an integral kernel, then K' is the maximal Q^ -inverse of K . Moreover, it holds that $Q \leq Q^*$.*

Proof. From the definition of K' , we simply find that

$$K'(y, z) \otimes Q(x, z) \leq K(x, y) \tag{28}$$

holds for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Hence, Q is (K, K') -compatible. Let Q be (K, K'') -compatible for some integral kernel $K'' : Y \times X \rightarrow L$. Since

$$K''(y, z) \otimes Q(x, z) \leq K(x, y)$$

for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$, we find that

$$K''(y, z) \leq \bigwedge_{x \in X} Q(x, z) \rightarrow K(x, y) = K'(y, z)$$

for any $z \in X$ and $y \in Y$, and thus $K'' \leq K'$. Hence, K' is the maximal integral kernel such that Q is (K, K') -compatible. From (28), for any $x, z \in X$, we obtain

$$Q(x, z) \leq K'(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y)$$

for any $y \in Y$, which implies

$$Q(x, z) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} K'(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y) = Q^*(x, z),$$

and thus $Q \leq Q^*$. Since Q is an integral kernel, the same holds for Q^* . By the definition, K' is the Q^* -inverse of K , and it remains to prove that K' is maximal. Let K'' be another Q^* -inverse of K . Since Q^* is (K, K'') -compatible and $Q \leq Q^*$, we have

$$K''(y, z) \otimes Q(x, z) \leq K''(y, z) \otimes Q^*(x, z) \leq K(x, y)$$

for any $x, z \in X$ and $y \in Y$, where we used the monotonicity of \otimes . Hence, Q is also (K, K'') -compatible, which implies that $K'' \leq K'$, since K' is the maximal integral kernel such that Q is (K, K') -compatible, which completes the proof. \square

The previous theorem provides a method for introducing an inverse kernel to K via a given integral kernel Q . More precisely, it guarantees the existence of a Q^* -inverse, where $Q \leq Q^*$. As a corollary, we find that K^T is always the maximal Q -inverse of K .

Corollary 5.2. *If K is an integral kernel, then K^T is the maximal Q -inverse of K .*

Proof. For any $x \in X$, we have

$$Q(x, x) = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} K^T(y, x) \rightarrow K(x, y) = \top,$$

which implies that Q is an integral kernel on X , and thus K^T is the Q -inverse of K . In addition, we find that

$$K^T(y, x) \leq \bigwedge_{u \in Y} Q(u, x) \rightarrow K(u, y) = K'(y, x),$$

for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$, and thus $K^T \leq K'$, where K' is the maximal Q^* -inverse of K according to Proposition 5.1. On the other side, we have

$$K'(y, x) = \bigwedge_{u \in Y} Q(u, x) \rightarrow K(u, y) \leq Q(x, x) \rightarrow K(x, y) =$$

$$\top \rightarrow K(x, y) = K(x, y) = K^T(y, x)$$

for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Hence, $K' \leq K^T$, which implies $K' = K^T$ and $Q = Q^*$. \square

The natural question is what is the position of the inverse defined as the transpose of an integral kernel among other inverses. The following proposition provides an answer to this question. Recall that a fuzzy relation Q on X is reflexive if $Q(x, x) = \top$ for any $x \in X$.

Proposition 5.3. *Let K be an integral kernel, and let K^{-1} be a Q -inverse of K . Assume that K is the P -inverse of K^{-1} for an integral kernel P on Y . If Q and P are reflexive fuzzy relations, then $K^{-1} = K^T$.*

Proof. Since Q is reflexive, we get

$$\top = Q(x, x) = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} K^{-1}(y, x) \rightarrow K(x, y)$$

for any $x \in X$, which implies $K^{-1}(y, x) \leq K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$, i.e., $K^{-1} \leq K^T$. By similar arguments, we find that

$$\top = P(y, y) = \bigwedge_{x \in X} K(x, y) \rightarrow K^{-1}(y, x)$$

for any $y \in Y$, which implies $K(x, y) \leq K^{-1}(y, x)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$, i.e., $K^T \leq K^{-1}$. Hence, we get $K^{-1} = K^T$. \square

The previous theorem shows that K^{-1} is uniquely determined as K^T if K and K^{-1} are mutually inverse for reflexive integral kernels Q and P , which seems to be a natural requirement and underscores the fundamental importance of the transpose integral kernel.

6. Approximation of functions based on lattice integral transforms

This section investigates the approximation of an original lattice-valued function using a composition of two distinct types of lattice integral transforms. We first demonstrate that such compositions yield either lower or upper approximations of the transformed original function via the integral kernel Q . This result generalizes the known upper and lower approximation properties of compositions for lattice fuzzy transforms, initially introduced in [27]. Next, we assess the quality of approximation using a modulus of continuity adapted for lattice-valued functions. Among other findings, we show that the closeness between the reconstructed and original functions - measured using the biresiduum operation in the residuated lattice - is guaranteed to exceed the value of the modulus of continuity of the original function. A key assumption underlying these results is the preservation of constant functions by the lattice integral transforms. The section concludes with an estimate of the closeness between the original and reconstructed functions expressed through the fuzzy integral of the square of the integral kernel Q , along with a reconstruction that achieves exact recovery of the original function. While these results rely on stronger assumptions, they are both intriguing and suggest promising directions for further research.

Throughout the analysis, we assume that $\langle X, \mathcal{F}, \mu_X \rangle$ and $\langle Y, \mathcal{G}, \mu_Y \rangle$ are fuzzy measure spaces, $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ represents an integral kernel, and $K^{-1} : Y \times X \rightarrow L$ is a Q -inverse of K .

6.1. Upper and lower approximation of functions

We begin with a theorem that extends the statement on the upper approximation using the lattice fuzzy transform (Theorems 6 and 8 in [27]). Specifically, we show that the composition of suitable lattice integral transforms yields an upper approximation – not of the original function itself, but of its transformed version under the integral kernel Q , that is, under the lattice integral transform $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\otimes} : \mathcal{F}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(X)$. Recall that the \otimes -fuzzy integral is a monotonically non-decreasing operator (see Proposition 3.2).

Theorem 6.1. *Let $F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}$ be a lattice integral transform from $\mathcal{F}(X)$ to $\mathcal{F}(Y)$, and let $F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}$ be a lattice integral transform from $\mathcal{F}(Y)$ to $\mathcal{F}(X)$. Then*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes} \geq F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}. \tag{29}$$

Proof. For any $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $z \in X$, using (ii) and (iv) of Proposition 3.2, we get

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) = \int_Y^{\otimes} (K^{-1}(y, z) \rightarrow F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y)) d\mu_Y =$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_Y \left(K^{-1}(y, z) \rightarrow \int_X K(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \geq \\ & \int_Y \left(\int_X \underline{(K^{-1}(y, z))}_X(x) \rightarrow (K(x, y) \otimes f(x)) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \geq \\ & \int_Y \left(\int_X \underline{(K^{-1}(y, z))}_X(x) \rightarrow K(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \geq \\ & \int_Y \left(\int_X Q(x, z) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \right) (y) d\mu_Y = \\ & \int_X Q(x, z) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X = F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^\otimes(f)(z), \end{aligned}$$

where we used $a \rightarrow (b \otimes c) \geq b \otimes (a \rightarrow c)$, which hold in each residuated lattice, $K^{-1}(y, z)$ is a constant for the fuzzy integral \int_X^\otimes (therefore, we may apply Proposition 3.2(iv)), the fact that Q is a (K, K^{-1}) -compatible, i.e., $\underline{(K^{-1}(y, z))}_X(x) \rightarrow K(x, y) = K^{-1}(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, y) \geq Q(x, z)$ for any $x, z \in X$, and

$$\left(\int_X Q(x, z) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \right)_Y$$

is a constant function on Y integrated by \int_Y^\otimes . \square

We can see that the composition of lattice integral transforms provides an upper approximation of the (Q, μ_X, \otimes) -lattice integral transform of the original function f . This type of lattice integral transform can act as a smoothing filter, removing high-frequency components from the original function, provided that (Q, μ_X) satisfies (C1), i.e., $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^\otimes$ preserves constant functions. In summary, the composition of lattice integral transforms provides an upper approximation of the transformed version of the original functions for the integral kernel Q , through which the inverse integral kernel K^{-1} is related to the integral kernel K .

Similarly, the following theorem generalizes the lower approximation of the original function using the composition of lattice integral transforms in the reverse order compared to the previous case. Here, the original function is transformed via the lattice integral transform $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow : \mathcal{F}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(X)$.

Theorem 6.2. Let $F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow$ be a lattice integral transform from $\mathcal{F}(X)$ to $\mathcal{F}(Y)$, and let $F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^\otimes$ be a lattice integral transform $\mathcal{F}(Y)$ to $\mathcal{F}(X)$. Then

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^\otimes \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow \leq F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow. \tag{30}$$

Proof. From Definition 5.2 and using (i) and (iii) of Proposition 3.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^\otimes \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow(f)(z) &= \int_Y^\otimes K^{-1}(y, z) \otimes F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow(f)(y) d\mu_Y = \\ & \int_Y^\otimes K^{-1}(y, z) \otimes \left(\int_X (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \leq \\ & \int_Y \left(\int_X \underline{K^{-1}(y, z)}_X(x) \otimes (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \leq \\ & \int_Y \left(\int_X \underline{((K^{-1}(y, z))_X(x) \rightarrow K(x, y)) \rightarrow K(x, y)} \otimes (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \leq \end{aligned}$$

Table 1
Parts of the integral kernels K and Q from Example 6.1.

x_i/y_j	1	4	7	10	13	16
1	1	1	0.6	0	0	0
2	1	1	0.8	0	0	0
3	1	1	1	0	0	0
4	1	1	1	0.6	0	0
5	1	1	1	0.8	0	0
6	0.8	1	1	1	0	0
7	0.6	1	1	1	0.6	0
8	0	1	1	1	0.8	0
9	0	0.8	1	1	1	0
10	0	0.6	1	1	1	0.6
11	0	0	1	1	1	0.8
12	0	0	0.8	1	1	1
13	0	0	0.6	1	1	1
14	0	0	0	1	1	1
15	0	0	0	0.8	1	1
16	0	0	0	0.6	1	1

(a) Integral kernel K

x_i/y_j	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42
1	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2	0	0	0	0
2	1	0.8	0.4	0.2	0	0	0	0
3	1	1	0.4	0.2	0	0	0	0
4	1	1	1	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2	0
5	1	1	1	1	0.8	0.4	0.2	0
6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	1	0.4	0.2	0
7	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	1	0.8	0.6
8	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.4	1	0.8
9	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.4	0.8	1
10	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

(b) Integral kernel Q

$$\int_Y \left(\int_X \left((K^{-1}(y, z) \rightarrow f(x)) \rightarrow K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) \right) d\mu_X \right) d\mu_Y \leq$$

$$\int_Y \left(\int_X Q(x, z) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X \right) (y) d\mu_Y =$$

$$\int_X Q(x, z) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X = F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z),$$

where we used $a \leq (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow b$ and $(a \rightarrow b) \otimes (b \rightarrow c) \leq a \rightarrow c$, which holds in each residuated lattice, the fact that the residuum is non-increasing in the first component, Q is a (K, K^{-1}) -compatible integral kernel (see the proof of Theorem 6.1 for details), and

$$\left(\int_X Q(x, z) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X \right)_Y$$

is a constant function integrated on Y by μ_Y^{\otimes} . \square

Note that (Q, μ_X, \rightarrow) -lattice integral transform on X with respect to the integral kernel Q acts as another smoothing filter, provided that (Q, μ_X) satisfies (C2), i.e., $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}$ preserves constant functions. Thus, the reverse composition of lattice integral transforms approximates from below the transformed version of original functions for the integral kernel Q .

Example 6.1. Let $X = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 100\}$ and $Y = \{1, 4, 7, \dots, 100\}$, i.e., $Y \subset X$. Assume that L is the Łukasiewicz algebra (see, Example 2.1). Consider the integral kernels $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$, $K^{-1} = K^T$, and Q , as defined in (24) of Definition 5.1. Parts of integral kernels K and Q are displayed in Table 1. It is evident that some of the cores of the y -projection of Q are singletons, as can be observed from the diagonal elements of the part of Q in case b). By Theorem 4.3, the maximal fuzzy measure μ_X^{\top} is the unique fuzzy measure that, together with Q , ensures the preservation of constant functions. Note that the lattice integral transform $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}$ can be interpreted as a “smoothing filter” in this case (see, an example of image filtering in [15]).

The verification of Theorem 6.1 is shown in Fig. 3(a), where we apply μ_X^{\top} (left) and a similar fuzzy measure μ_X (right) that is not maximal, but (K, μ_X) satisfies (C1) in contrast to (Q, μ_X) . Moreover, we consider μ_Y , which, together with K^{-1} , ensures the preservation of constant functions. In the case of μ_X^{\top} , nearly all function values of the original function (colored in black) remain unchanged after the transformation (colored in green). However, when using μ , which does not ensure the preservation of constant functions, the results differ significantly and the output is not practical for use. This highlights the importance of the constant function preservation assumption in applications mentioned in Section 4. In both cases of fuzzy measures μ_X^{\top} and μ_X , the reconstructions of the original function given by the composition of lattice integral transforms $F_{(K, \mu_X^{\top})}^{\otimes}$ or $F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}$ with $F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}$ (colored by red) dominate the outputs of $F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}$, which confirms the desired statement. Moreover, we observe that both reconstructions are very similar. This similarity arises from the similarity between the measures μ^{\top} and μ , as well as the assumption of constant function preservation by

Fig. 3. Verification of the upper and lower approximation using the composition of lattice integral transforms from Example 6.1.

the integral transforms of the lattice. This preservation is ensured by the configuration of the integral kernels K and K^{-1} , along with the fuzzy measures μ_X^\top, μ_X , and μ_Y , respectively.²

The verification of Theorem 6.2 is shown in Fig. 3(b), where we apply the conjugate fuzzy measure to μ_X^\top , which is μ_X^\perp , and a fuzzy measure μ_X such that (Q, μ_X) does not satisfy (C2). As the commentary on the results is similar to the previous case, it is omitted here.

As a consequence of the previous theorems, we can derive another approximation of the original function using compositions of lattice integral transforms. Recall that Q_y denotes the y -projection of Q into X , i.e., $Q_y(x) = Q(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$

Corollary 6.3. For any $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ and $y \in X$, it holds that

- (i) $F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^\rightarrow \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\otimes (f)(y) \geq \int_X^\otimes f \otimes \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} d\mu_X$,
- (ii) $F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^\otimes \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^\rightarrow (f)(y) \leq \int_X^\otimes \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} \rightarrow f d\mu_X$.

Proof. Let $\Delta : L \rightarrow L$ be the Baaz-Monteiro delta [1] given as follows

$$\Delta(a) = \begin{cases} \top, & a = \top, \\ \perp, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{31}$$

and define $\Delta Q : X \times X \rightarrow L$ as $\Delta Q(x, y) = \Delta(Q(x, y))$ for any $x, y \in X$. Obviously, $\Delta Q \leq Q$. In addition, for any $y \in X$ there is $x \in X$ such that $\Delta Q(x, y) = \top$, since Q is an integral kernel on X .

(i) By Proposition 3.2(i), for any $y \in Y$, we simply get

$$F_{(Q, \mu)}^\otimes (f)(y) = \int_X^\otimes Q(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X$$

² Note that the reconstructions are computed using an algorithm that extends the given function on both the left and right sides by appropriately repeating the first and last function values. This technique helps minimize calculation errors at the boundaries of the function domain.

$$\geq \int_X^{\otimes} \Delta Q(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X = \int_X^{\otimes} f(x) \otimes \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} d\mu_X,$$

where we used that \otimes is monotonically non-decreasing in both arguments. The statement follows directly from (29).

(ii) Similarly, by Proposition 3.2(i), for any $y \in Y$, we simply get

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) &= \int_X^{\otimes} Q(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X \\ &\leq \int_X^{\otimes} \Delta Q(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X = \int_X^{\otimes} \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X, \end{aligned}$$

where we used that \rightarrow is monotonically non-increasing in the first component. The statement directly from (30). \square

At the end of the section, we demonstrate that the upper and lower approximations of lattice-valued functions using the compositions of lattice fuzzy transform are simple consequences of the statements above, even for more general integral kernels that do not necessarily form a fuzzy partition of X (see, Remark 4.1).

Corollary 6.4. *Let K be an integral kernel, and let K^{-1} be the Q -inverse of K such that Q is a reflexive integral kernel. Then, for any $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$, it holds that*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y^{\top})}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X^{\perp})}^{\rightarrow}(f) \leq f \leq F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y^{\perp})}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X^{\top})}^{\otimes}(f). \tag{32}$$

Proof. Let $y \in X$. From Corollary 6.3(i), we get

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y^{\perp})}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X^{\top})}^{\otimes}(f)(y) &\geq \int_X^{\otimes} f \otimes \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} d\mu_X^{\top} = \\ \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A} f(x) \otimes \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)}(x) \right) \otimes \mu_X^{\top}(A) &= \bigvee_{x \in \text{Core}(Q_y)} f(x) \geq f(y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used the fact that Q is reflexive, and thus $y \in \text{Core}(Q_y)$. Hence, the right inequality in (32) is proved.

From Corollary 6.3(ii), we get

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y^{\top})}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X^{\perp})}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) &\leq \int_X^{\otimes} \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)} \rightarrow f d\mu_X^{\perp} = \\ \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A} \top_{\text{Core}(Q_y)}(x) \rightarrow f(x) \right) \otimes \mu_X^{\perp}(A) &= \bigwedge_{x \in \text{Core}(Q_y)} f(x) \leq f(y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used again the fact that $y \in \text{Core}(Q_y)$, and the fact $\top \rightarrow a = a$. Hence, the left inequality in (32) is proved. \square

6.2. Estimation of approximation quality

In this part, we focus on the quality estimation of the approximation of the original function using the lattice integral transforms and their compositions. One tool to measure the quality of the approximation is to determine the proximity of the original function and the reconstructed function with respect to the modulus of continuity.³ For the classical (higher degree) fuzzy transform, we can find several approximation theorems based on the modulus of continuity, see, for example, [3,13,29]. In the case of a lattice-valued function, it is difficult to apply the arithmetic of real numbers; therefore, we propose the following, more abstract, definition of modulus of continuity suitable for our purpose. Let $\mathcal{E}(X)$ denote the set of all relations on X such that for any $E \in \mathcal{E}(X)$ there is a family $\mathcal{E}(E) = \{E_i \in \mathcal{E}(X) \mid i \in I\}$ for which

³ Recall that the *modulus of continuity* is a function that quantitatively describes the uniform continuity of a given function. Formally, for a real-valued function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the modulus of continuity is a function $\omega_f : [0, \infty] \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ given as:

$$\omega_f(\delta) := \sup_{\substack{x, y \in \mathbb{R} \\ |x - y| \leq \delta}} |f(x) - f(y)|, \quad \delta \in [0, \infty],$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value, and sup is the supremum on the set of real numbers.

- (i) E_i is a equivalence on X for any $i \in I$,
- (ii) $\bigcup \mathcal{E}(E) = E$.

Observe that $\mathcal{E}(X)$ consists of all equivalences on X and their unions.⁴

Definition 6.1. Let $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$. The function $\omega_f : \mathcal{E}(X) \rightarrow L$ given by

$$\omega_f(E) = \bigwedge_{(x,y) \in E} f(x) \leftrightarrow f(y) \tag{33}$$

is called the $\mathcal{E}(X)$ -modulus of continuity of f .

The $\mathcal{E}(X)$ -modulus of continuity of a function f characterizes how close the function values are at points that are considered close with respect to a given relation $E \in \mathcal{E}(X)$. In the trivial case where E represents equality on X , we have $\omega_f(E) = \top$. Larger values of the $\mathcal{E}(X)$ -modulus of continuity indicate greater smoothness of the function f , meaning that the values of f vary little between points that are close under the relation E .

First, we analyze how the function values resulting from the lattice integral transform are close to the values of the original function under a given equivalence relation. Recall that a constant function on X is denoted by \underline{a}_X . The following theorem shows an estimate of the approximation quality for the \otimes -lattice integral transform.

Theorem 6.5. Let (K, μ) satisfy (C1), and let $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ and $y \in Y$. Define an equivalence E_y on X as $(x, z) \in E_y$, if $x = z$ or $x, z \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$, for any $x, z \in X$. Then

$$F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \omega_f(E_y), \tag{34}$$

for any $x \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$.

Proof. Let $y \in Y$. It is easy to see that E_y is an equivalence of X , so $E_y \in \mathcal{E}(X)$. Further, let us show that the \otimes -lattice integral transform can be expressed as follows

$$F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) = \bigvee_{\substack{A \in \mathcal{F} \\ A \subseteq \text{Supp}(K_y)}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A} (K(x, y) \otimes f(x)) \otimes \mu(A) \right).$$

Note that the satisfaction of (C1) by (K, μ) ensures that there is $A \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A \subseteq \text{Supp}(K_y)$ with $\mu(A) = \top$, i.e., $A \neq \emptyset$. In addition, if $A \not\subseteq \text{Supp}(K_y)$, then there is $x \in A$ such that $K(x, y) = \perp$, which implies $\bigwedge_{x \in A} K(x, y) \otimes f(x) = \perp$; therefore, it is sufficient to restrict the supremum to all \mathcal{F} -measurable sets that are subsets of $\text{Supp}(A)$. Denote by \mathcal{F}_y the set of all such \mathcal{F} -measurable sets. Let $x \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$. Since $F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}$ preserves constant functions due to (C1), using (13), (17) and (18) of Proposition 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x) &= F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(\underline{f(x)}_X)(y) = \\ &\bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in A} (K(z, y) \otimes f(z)) \otimes \mu(A) \right) \leftrightarrow \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in A} (K(z, y) \otimes \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \otimes \mu(A) \right) \geq \\ &\bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in A} (K(z, y) \otimes f(z)) \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{z \in A} (K(z, y) \otimes \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \right) \otimes (\mu(A) \leftrightarrow \mu(A)) \geq \\ &\bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \bigwedge_{z \in A} (K(z, y) \leftrightarrow K(z, y)) \otimes (f(z) \leftrightarrow \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \geq \\ &\bigwedge_{z \in \text{Supp}(K_y)} (f(z) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{(u,v) \in E_y} (f(u) \leftrightarrow f(v)) = \omega_f(E_y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used the fact that $x, z \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$ implies $(x, z) \in E_y$. \square

Observe that the pairs $(x, x) \in E_y$ have no effect on the $\mathcal{E}(X)$ -modulus of continuity of f , since $f(x) \leftrightarrow f(x) = \top$ holds. Thus, the equivalence E_y induces a “local” closeness on X ; more precisely, the points in $\text{Supp}(K_y)$ are all mutually close under this relation. The previous theorem shows that the value of the transformed function f at the point y , namely $F_{(K,\mu)}^{\otimes}(f)(y)$, is close to $f(x)$ (an original function value) to a degree that exceeds the original degree of closeness of function values over $\text{Supp}(K_y)$, as measured by the

⁴ Note that $\mathcal{E}(X)$ is a collection of relations on X that express a notion of “closeness” or “proximity” on X . For instance, the condition $|x - y| \leq \delta$, which appears in the definition of modulus of continuity, captures the δ -closeness of elements x and y in \mathbb{R} in terms of distance. This δ -closeness can be reformulated using a relation from $\mathcal{E}(\mathbb{R})$ as follows. For any $\delta \in [0, \infty]$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$, define $(y, z) \in E_{\delta,x}$ for $y, z \in \mathbb{R}$, if either $y = z$ or $y, z \in [x - \frac{\delta}{2}, x + \frac{\delta}{2}]$. Obviously, $E_{\delta,x}$ is an equivalence on X . Put $E_{\delta} = \bigcup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} E_{\delta,x}$. Then $|x - y| \leq \delta$ if and only if $(x, y) \in E_{\delta}$. It is important to note that E_{δ} is not equivalence on X , since it generally fails to satisfy transitivity.

$\mathcal{E}(X)$ -modulus of continuity $\omega_f(E_y)$. The next theorem provides a similar estimation of the approximation quality for the \rightarrow -lattice integral transform.

Theorem 6.6. *Let (K, μ) satisfy (C2), and let $f \in \mathcal{F}(X)$ and $y \in Y$. Define the equivalence E_y on X as in Theorem 6.5. Then*

$$F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \omega_f(E_y), \tag{35}$$

for any $x \in \text{Core}(K_y)$.

Proof. From Theorem 6.5, we know that $E_y \in \mathcal{E}(X)$. First, let us show that the lattice integral transform can be expressed as follows

$$F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) = \bigvee_{\substack{A \in \mathcal{F} \\ A \cap \text{Core}(K_y) \neq \emptyset}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A \cap \text{Supp}(K_y)} (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) \otimes \mu(A) \right).$$

Since (K, μ) satisfies (C2), i.e., $\mu(A) = \perp$ for any $A \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(K_y)$, we can write

$$F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) = \bigvee_{\substack{A \in \mathcal{F} \\ A \cap \text{Core}(K_y) \neq \emptyset}} \left(\bigwedge_{x \in A} (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) \otimes \mu(A) \right). \tag{36}$$

In addition, we have

$$\bigwedge_{x \in A} (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)) = \bigwedge_{x \in A \cap \text{Supp}(K_y)} (K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)),$$

where we used that $K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) = \perp \rightarrow f(x) = \top$ for any $x \in A$ such that $x \notin \text{Supp}(K_y)$, which verifies the desired modification of the definition of $F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)$. Denote by \mathcal{F}_y the set of all \mathcal{F} -measurable sets A such that $A \cap \text{Core}(K_y) \neq \emptyset$ and put $S(A, K_y) = A \cap \text{Supp}(K_y)$. Obviously, $S(A, K_y) \subseteq S(B, K_y)$ if $A \subseteq B$. Since $F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}$ preserves constant functions due to (C2), using (10), (14), (17) and (18) of Proposition 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x) &= F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow F_{(K,\mu)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{f(x)}_X)(y) = \\ &= \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in S(A, K_y)} (K(z, y) \rightarrow f(z)) \otimes \mu(A) \right) \leftrightarrow \\ &= \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in S(A, K_y)} (K(z, y) \rightarrow \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \otimes \mu(A) \right) \geq \\ &= \bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \left(\bigwedge_{z \in S(A, K_y)} (K(z, y) \rightarrow f(z)) \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{z \in S(A, K_y)} (K(z, y) \rightarrow \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \right) \otimes (\mu(A) \leftrightarrow \mu(A)) \geq \\ &= \bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \bigwedge_{z \in S(A, K_y)} (K(z, y) \leftrightarrow K(z, y)) \otimes (f(z) \leftrightarrow \underline{f(x)}_X(z)) \geq \\ &= \bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{F}_y} \bigwedge_{z \in S(A, y)} (f(z) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{z \in S(X, K_y)} (f(z) \leftrightarrow f(x)) = \\ &= \bigwedge_{z \in \text{Supp}(K_y)} (f(z) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{(u,v) \in E_y} (f(u) \leftrightarrow f(v)) = \omega_f(E_y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used the similar notation and arguments as in the proof of Theorem 6.5. \square

The following statements provide an assessment of the approximation quality of the reconstructed functions. Precisely, we demonstrate that the closeness between the original and reconstructed function values for a given function, quantified by the biresiduum in the residuated lattice, is always greater than or equal to the modulus of continuity of the function f . For this purpose, we use the relation $E \in \mathcal{E}(X)$ defined as

$$E = \bigcup_{y \in Y} E_y, \tag{37}$$

where each E_y is the equivalence relation introduced in Theorem 6.5. This relation E induces a form of global closeness on X by aggregating the local closeness relations E_y associated with each point $y \in Y$. Observe that

$$\omega_f(E) = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} \omega_f(E_y). \tag{38}$$

Indeed, since $E_y \subseteq E$ for any $y \in Y$, it follows that $\omega_f(E) \leq \omega_f(E_y)$, and thus, $\omega_f(E) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} \omega_f(E_y)$. Conversely, for any $(x, z) \in E$, there exists some $y \in Y$ such that $(x, z) \in E_y$. Consequently, $f(x) \leftrightarrow f(z) \geq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} \omega_f(E_y)$ for any $(x, z) \in E$, which implies $\omega_f(E) \geq \bigwedge_{y \in Y} \omega_f(E_y)$.

Theorem 6.7. Let K be an integral kernel, K^{-1} be a Q -inverse of K for a reflexive integral kernel Q , and let $f \in F(X)$. Assume that (K, μ_X) satisfies (C1) and (K^{-1}, μ_Y) satisfies (C2). Then

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \omega_f(E) \tag{39}$$

for any $x \in X$, where E is given in (37).

Proof. Since Q is reflexive, we get $\top = Q(x, x) = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} K^{-1}(y, x) \rightarrow K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$, which implies $K^{-1}(y, x) \leq K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Hence, we get that if $y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})$, then $x \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$. Similarly to the proof of Theorem 6.6, for any $x \in X$, denote \mathcal{G}_x the set of all \mathcal{G} -measurable sets B on Y such that $B \cap \text{Core}(K_x^{-1}) \neq \emptyset$ and put $S(B, K_x^{-1}) = B \cap \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})$. Let $x \in X$. Since both lattice integral transforms preserve constant functions, using Theorem 6.5, formula (36) and the fact that $x \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$ for any $y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow f(x) = \\ & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(\underline{f(x)}_X)(x) = \\ & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}(F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f))(x) \leftrightarrow F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{f(x)}_Y)(x) = \\ & \bigvee_{B \in \mathcal{G}_x} \left(\bigwedge_{y \in S(B, K_x^{-1})} (K^{-1}(y, x) \rightarrow F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y)) \otimes \mu_Y(B) \right) \leftrightarrow \\ & \bigvee_{B \in \mathcal{G}_x} \left(\bigwedge_{y \in S(B, K_x^{-1})} (K^{-1}(y, x) \rightarrow \underline{f(x)}_Y(y)) \otimes \mu_Y(B) \right) \geq \\ & \bigwedge_{B \in \mathcal{G}_x} \bigwedge_{y \in S(B, K_x^{-1})} (F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow \underline{f(x)}_Y(y)) = \bigwedge_{y \in S(Y, K_x^{-1})} (F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \\ & = \bigwedge_{y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})} (F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})} \omega_f(E_y) \geq \omega_f(E), \end{aligned}$$

where we applied (38) and omitted the analogous steps from the proof of Theorem 6.6. \square

Theorem 6.8. Let K be an integral kernel, K^{-1} be a Q -inverse of K for a reflexive integral kernel Q , and let $f \in F(X)$. Assume that (K, μ_X) satisfies (C2) and (K^{-1}, μ_Y) satisfies (C1). Then

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow f(x) \geq \omega_f(E) \tag{40}$$

for any $x \in X$, where E is given in (37).

Proof. Similarly to the proof of Theorem 6.5, denote \mathcal{G}_x the set of all \mathcal{G} -measurable sets A such that $A \subseteq \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})$. Let $x \in X$. Since both lattice integral transforms preserve constant functions, using Theorem 6.6, formula (34) and the fact that $x \in \text{Supp}(K_y)$ for any $y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})$ (see the proof of Theorem 6.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow f(x) = \\ & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{f(x)}_X)(x) = \\ & F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes}(F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f))(x) \leftrightarrow F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes}(\underline{f(x)}_Y)(x) \geq \\ & \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{G}_x} \left(\bigwedge_{y \in A} (K^{-1}(y, x) \otimes F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y)) \otimes \mu_Y(A) \right) \leftrightarrow \\ & \bigvee_{A \in \mathcal{G}_x} \left(\bigwedge_{y \in A} (K^{-1}(y, x) \otimes \underline{f(x)}_Y(y)) \otimes \mu_Y(A) \right) \geq \\ & \bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{G}_x} \bigwedge_{y \in A} (F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow \underline{f(x)}_Y(y)) = \\ & \bigwedge_{A \in \mathcal{G}_x} \bigwedge_{y \in A} (F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) \leftrightarrow f(x)) \geq \bigwedge_{y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})} \omega_f(E_y) \geq \omega_f(E), \end{aligned}$$

where we applied (38) and omitted analogous steps from the proof of Theorem 6.5. \square

It is worth noting that the inequalities (39) and (40) remain true, if for each $x \in X$, the relation E is replaced by the more specific relation

Table 2
Values of closeness between the original and reconstructed functions and modulus of continuity from Example 6.2.

	f	g
$F^{\rightarrow, \otimes}(\cdot) \leftrightarrow \cdot$	0.962138	0.724528
$F^{\otimes, \rightarrow}(\cdot) \leftrightarrow \cdot$	0.891274	0.633113
$\omega_r(E)$	0.887333	0.410865

$$E_x = \bigcup_{y \in \text{Supp}(K_x^{-1})} E_y,$$

follows directly from the proof of the preceding theorems. The following example illustrates the results of Theorem 6.7 and Theorem 6.8.

Example 6.2. Assume that $X = \{1, 2, \dots, 401\}$ and $Y = \{1, 6, \dots, 401\}$, L is the Łukasiewicz algebra (see, Example 2.1) and the integral kernel $K : X \times Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is given as follows:

$$K(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & |x - y| \leq 7, \\ 0.9, & 7 < |x - y| \leq 9 \\ 0.8, & 9 < |x - y| \leq 12, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, we define $K^{-1} = K^T$. Fuzzy measures on $\langle X, \mathcal{P}(X) \rangle$ and $\langle Y, \mathcal{P}(Y) \rangle$ are determined as relative fuzzy measures $\mu_{\varphi_X}^r$ and $\mu_{\varphi_Y}^r$ modified by the functions $\varphi_X, \varphi_Y : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$. These functions are defined as follows:

$$\varphi_X(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq \frac{2}{401}, \\ 140.35 \left(x - \frac{2}{401}\right), & \frac{2}{401} < x \leq \frac{4}{401}, \\ 0.7 + 30.075 \left(x - \frac{4}{401}\right), & \frac{4}{401} < x \leq \frac{8}{401}, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\varphi_Y(x) = \begin{cases} 48.6x, & x \leq \frac{1}{81}, \\ 0.6 + 32.4 \left(x - \frac{1}{81}\right), & \frac{1}{81} < x \leq \frac{2}{81}, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It is straightforward to verify that both fuzzy measures, together with the kernel K , satisfy condition (C1). The N -conjugate fuzzy measures of $\mu_{\varphi_X}^r$ and $\mu_{\varphi_Y}^r$ are constructed using Definition 3.4 with the negation $N(x) = 1 - x$ for $x \in [0, 1]$. Consequently, these N -conjugate fuzzy measures, together with K^{-1} , satisfy condition (C2). We examine two functions, illustrated in Fig. 4, referred to as f (case (a)) and g (case (b)). For simplicity, we define:

$$F^{\rightarrow, \otimes}(f)(x) = F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_{\varphi_Y}^r)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_{\varphi_X}^r)}^{\otimes}(f)(x),$$

and similarly for $F^{\otimes, \rightarrow}(f)(x)$, $F^{\rightarrow, \otimes}(g)(x)$, and $F^{\otimes, \rightarrow}(g)(x)$. Additionally, we use the notation:

$$F^{\rightarrow, \otimes}(f) \leftrightarrow f = \bigwedge_{x \in X} (F^{\rightarrow, \otimes}(f)(x) \leftrightarrow f(x)),$$

and similarly for other cases. The values used to verify the inequalities in Theorems 6.7 and 6.8 are summarized in Table 2. As can be observed, the inequality holds in all cases. The composition of lattice integral transforms beginning with the \otimes -lattice integral transform yields slightly better results compared to the reverse composition. This difference may be attributed to the choice of fuzzy measures on the domains X and Y , which appear to favor the first type of composition.

In the last part of this subsection, we derive an estimation of the approximation quality of lattice integral transforms for special functions which are extensional with respect to a fuzzy relation Q on the space X . We restrict our consideration to the case where $Y \subseteq X$ and $K^{-1} = K^T$. From Corollary 5.2, we know that K^T is a maximal Q -inverse of K , where Q is the integral kernel on X given by formula (24).

Let $Y \subseteq X$ be a non-empty set, and let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be an integral kernel. We say that K is Y -reflexive if $K(y, y) = \top$ for any $y \in Y$, and K is Y -transitive if $K(x, y) \otimes K^T(y, z) \leq K(x, z)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y, z \in Y$. Furthermore, define a fuzzy relation $P : X \times X \rightarrow L$ as follows

Fig. 4. The approximation of two functions f and g (black) using the compositions of lattice integral kernel from Example 6.2.

$$P(x, y) = \bigvee_{z \in Y} K(x, z) \otimes K^T(z, y) \tag{41}$$

for any $x, y \in X$. The following lemma establishes a relationship between Y -transitivity and the fuzzy relations P and Q , which will be utilized later.

Lemma 6.9. *Let $Y \subseteq X$ be a non-empty set, let K be a Y -reflexive integral kernel, and let K^T be a Q -inverse of K . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) K is Y -transitive,
- (ii) $P(x, y) = K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$,
- (iii) $Q(x, y) = K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$.

Proof. $(i) \Rightarrow (ii)$ By the Y -transitivity of K , it is straightforward to see that $K(x, y) \geq P(x, y)$ for $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. For the reverse inequality, we have

$$P(x, y) \geq K(x, y) \otimes K^T(y, y) = K(x, y) \otimes K(y, y) = K(x, y) \otimes \top = K(x, y),$$

where we used Y -reflexivity of K . Combining these two inequalities, we get the desired equality.

$(ii) \Rightarrow (iii)$ From (41) and Y -reflexivity of K , we can observe for $y, z \in Y$

$$K(y, z) = \bigvee_{u \in Y} K(y, u) \otimes K^T(u, z) \geq K(y, y) \otimes K^T(y, z) = K^T(y, z).$$

By interchanging the coordinates of K , using the same arguments we get $K^T(y, z) \geq K(y, z)$. Hence, $K(y, z) = K^T(y, z)$ for any $y, z \in Y$ and the fuzzy relation K restricted to $Y \times Y$ is symmetric. Further, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Q(x, y) &= \bigwedge_{z \in Y} K^T(z, y) \rightarrow K(x, z) = \bigwedge_{z \in Y} K(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, z) \leq \\ &K(y, y) \rightarrow K(x, y) = \top \rightarrow K(x, z) = K(x, z), \end{aligned}$$

where we used $\top \rightarrow a = a$ for any $a \in L$, which holds in any residuated lattice. By assumption (ii), for any $z \in Y$, we have

$$K(x, z) = P(x, z) = \bigvee_{u \in Y} K(x, u) \otimes K^T(u, z) \geq K(x, y) \otimes K^T(y, z),$$

which, by the adjointness and the fact that K restricted to $Y \times Y$ is symmetric, implies

$$K(x, y) \leq K^T(y, z) \rightarrow K(x, z) = K^T(z, y) \rightarrow K(x, z).$$

Since the previous inequality holds for any $z \in Y$, we find that

$$K(x, y) \leq \bigwedge_{z \in Y} K^T(z, y) \rightarrow K(x, z) = Q(x, z).$$

Combining both inequalities, we obtain $K(x, y) = Q(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) It is easy to see that $K(x, y) = Q(x, y) \leq K^T(z, y) \rightarrow K(x, z)$ for any $z \in Y$. By the adjointness and the fact that K restricted to $Y \times Y$ is symmetric, we find that $K(x, y) \otimes K^T(y, z) \leq K(x, z)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y, z \in Y$, which implies that K is Y -transitive. \square

As a direct consequence of the previous lemma, we conclude that if K is Y -reflexive and Y -transitive, then the fuzzy relations P and Q restricted to $X \times Y$ inherit these properties, i.e., they are Y -reflexive and Y -transitive as well. In addition, all fuzzy relations K , P and Q coincides on $Y \times Y$ and are similarity relations.

Let $f : X \rightarrow L$ be a function, and let R be a fuzzy relation on X . We say that f is *extensional with respect to R* if

$$f(x) \otimes R(x, y) \leq f(y) \text{ and } R(x, y) \otimes f(y) \leq f(x) \tag{42}$$

holds for any $x, y \in X$. Note that the standard concept of extensionality of f is typically defined with respect to a similarity relation R on X , and due to the symmetry of R , it is sufficient to consider only one of the relevant inequalities. However, in our case, we do not impose any specific properties on R in general. As a result, both inequalities must be considered to properly define the extensionality of f with respect to R . The following theorems provide an estimation of the approximation of extensional functions.

Theorem 6.10. *Let $Y \subseteq X$ be a non-empty set, let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be an integral kernel, which is Y -reflexive and Y -transitive, and let $K^{-1} = K^T$ be a Q -inverse of K . If f is extensional with respect to Q and (K^{-1}, μ_Y) satisfies (C2), then*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) \leftrightarrow f(z) \geq \int_X Q^2(x, z) d\mu_X \tag{43}$$

for any $z \in X$.

Proof. Let f be an extensional function with respect to Q . By Lemma 6.9, it follows that $K(x, y) = Q(x, y)$ for all $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Consequently, the inverse relation satisfies $K^{-1}(y, x) = Q^T(y, x)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. For any $y \in Y$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) &= \int_X K(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X = \\ &= \int_X Q(x, y) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \leq \int_X \underline{f(y)}_X(x) d\mu_X = f(y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used (i) and (ii) of Proposition 3.2, and the extensionality of f with respect to Q . It is easy to see that $K^2(x, y) = Q^2(x, y) = Q(x, y) \otimes Q(x, y)$ for $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$ is again an integral kernel, since $\top = \top \otimes \top$. Note that $(K^2)^T = (K^T)^2 = (K^{-1})^2$. In addition, it holds that $\text{Core}(K_x^{-1}) = \text{Core}(K_x^T) = \text{Core}((K^2)_x^T)$ for any $x \in X$. Indeed, if $y \in \text{Core}(K_x^T)$, then $K^T(y, x) = \top = (K^2)^T(y, x)$; therefore, $y \in \text{Core}((K^2)_x^T)$. If $y \in \text{Core}((K^2)_x^T)$, then $(K^2)^T(y, x) = (K^T)^2 = \top$. Since \top is the only solution of the equation $a \otimes a = \top$, we get $K^T(y, x) = \top$; therefore, $y \in \text{Core}(K_x^T)$. Since (K^T, μ_Y) satisfies (C2), we find that $((K^2)^T, \mu_Y)$ also satisfies (C2). Hence, for any $z \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) &= \int_Y K^{-1}(y, z) \rightarrow F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) d\mu_Y = \\ &= \int_Y Q^T(y, z) \rightarrow F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) d\mu_Y \leq \int_Y Q^T(y, z) \rightarrow f(y) d\mu_Y \leq \\ &= \int_Y (Q^T(y, z) \otimes Q^T(y, z)) \rightarrow (Q^T(y, z) \otimes f(y)) d\mu_Y = \\ &= \int_Y (Q^T)^2(y, z) \rightarrow (Q(z, y) \otimes f(y)) d\mu_Y \leq \int_Y (Q^2)^T(y, z) \rightarrow \underline{f(z)}_Y(y) d\mu_Y = \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_Y^{\otimes} (K^2)^T(y, z) \rightarrow \underline{f(z)}_Y(y) d\mu_Y = F_{((K^2)^T, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{f(z)}_Y)(z) = f(z),$$

where we used $b \rightarrow c \leq (a \otimes b) \rightarrow (a \otimes c)$, which holds in each residuated lattice, the inequality $F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(y) \leq f(y)$ demonstrated above, the monotonicity of the residuum in the second argument, Proposition 3.2(i), and the fact that $((K^2)^T, \mu_Y)$ satisfies (C2), and therefore, $F_{((K^2)^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}$ preserves constant functions. As a consequence of the previous inequality, we obtain

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) \rightarrow f(z) = \top \tag{44}$$

for any $z \in X$. Furthermore, for any $x, z \in X$, we have $Q(x, z) \otimes f(z) \leq f(x)$ due to the extensionality of f with respect to Q . Using Proposition 3.2(iii) and Theorem 6.1, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) &\geq F_{(Q, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) = \int_X^{\otimes} Q(x, z) \otimes f(x) d\mu_X \geq \\ &\int_X^{\otimes} Q(x, z) \otimes (Q(x, z) \otimes \underline{f(z)}_X(x)) d\mu_X = \int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, z) \otimes \underline{f(z)}_X(x) d\mu_X \geq \\ &f(z) \otimes \int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, z) d\mu_X, \end{aligned}$$

By the adjointness property, we get

$$f(z) \rightarrow (F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes})(f)(z) \geq \int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, z) d\mu_X \tag{45}$$

for any $z \in X$. Combining (44) and (45), we get the desired inequality in (43). \square

Theorem 6.11. *Let $Y \subseteq X$ be a non-empty set, let $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ be an integral kernel, which is Y -reflexive and Y -transitive, and let $K^{-1} = K^T$ be a Q -inverse of K . If f is extensional with respect to Q and (K, μ_X) satisfies (C2), then*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) \leftrightarrow f(z) \geq \int_Y^{\otimes} Q^2(z, y) d\mu_Y \tag{46}$$

for any $z \in X$.

Proof. Let f be an extensional function with respect to Q . From the proof of Theorem 6.10, we know that $K^{-1}(y, x) = Q^T(y, x)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. First, we show that under the assumptions of the theorem, it holds that

$$F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) = f(y), \quad y \in Y. \tag{47}$$

Obviously, $\text{Core}(K_y) \subseteq \text{Core}(Q_y^2)$ for any $y \in Y$, where $Q_y^2(x) = Q_y(x) \otimes Q_y(x)$ for $x \in X$. Indeed, due to Lemma 6.9, we have $K_y(x) = K(x, y) = Q(x, y) = Q_y(x)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Hence, if $x \in \text{Core}(K_y)$, then $K_y(x) = \top = Q_y(x)$, therefore, $Q_y^2(x) = \top$ and $x \in \text{Core}(Q_y^2)$. Now, if $A \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $A \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(Q_y^2)$, then $A \subseteq X \setminus \text{Core}(K_y)$, which implies $\mu_X(A) = \perp$, since (K, μ_X) satisfies (C2). As a consequence, we obtain that (Q^2, μ_X) also satisfies (C2), and $F_{(Q^2, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}$ preserves constant functions. Then, for any $y \in Y$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) &= \int_X^{\otimes} K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X = \int_X^{\otimes} Q(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X \leq \\ &\int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, y) \rightarrow (f(x) \otimes Q(x, y)) d\mu_X \leq \int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, y) \rightarrow \underline{f(y)}_X(x) d\mu_X = \\ &F_{(Q^2, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{f(y)}_X)(y) = f(y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used $b \rightarrow c \leq (a \otimes b) \rightarrow (a \otimes c)$ and the extensionality of f with respect to Q . On the other hand, for any $x, y \in X$, the inequality $Q(x, y) \otimes f(y) \leq f(x)$ implies $f(y) \leq Q(x, y) \rightarrow f(x)$ as a consequence of the adjointness property. Using Proposition 3.2(ii), we directly obtain

$$F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) = \int_X K(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X = \int_X Q(x, y) \rightarrow f(x) d\mu_X \geq \int_X \underline{f(y)}_X(x) d\mu_X = f(y),$$

which, combined with the previous inequality, establishes (47). Using this equality, for any $z \in X$, we get

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) = \int_Y K^{-1}(y, z) \otimes F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) d\mu_Y = \int_Y Q^T(y, z) \otimes f(y) d\mu_Y = \int_Y Q(z, y) \otimes f(y) d\mu_Y \leq \int_Y \underline{f(z)}_Y(y) d\mu_Y = f(z),$$

where we used Proposition 3.2(ii) and the extensionality of f with respect to Q . As a consequence of this inequality, we get

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) \rightarrow f(z) = \top. \tag{48}$$

Since $f(z) \otimes Q(z, y) = f(z) \otimes Q^T(y, z) \leq f(y)$ for any $z \in X$ and $y \in Y$, we get

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) = \int_Y Q^T(y, z) \otimes F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(y) d\mu_Y = \int_Y Q^T(y, z) \otimes f(y) d\mu_Y \geq \int_Y Q^T(y, x) \otimes (Q^T(y, x) \otimes \underline{f(x)}_Y(y)) d\mu_Y = \int_Y (Q^T)^2(y, z) \otimes \underline{f(z)}_Y(y) d\mu_Y \geq f(z) \otimes \int_Y (Q^T)^2(y, z) d\mu_Y,$$

where we used Proposition 3.2(iii) and (47). Due to the adjointness property, we find that

$$f(z) \rightarrow F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) \geq \int_Y Q^2(z, y) d\mu_Y, \tag{49}$$

where we used the fact that $(Q^T)^2(y, z) = Q^2(z, y)$, which follows from $(Q^T)^2(y, z) = Q^T(y, z) \otimes Q^T(y, z) = Q(z, y) \otimes Q(z, y) = Q^2(z, y)$ for any $z \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Combining (48) and (49), we obtain the desired inequality in (46). \square

Example 6.3. To concisely illustrate the preceding theorems, we consider a small domain for functions, namely $X = \{1, 2, \dots, 15\}$, along with its subset $Y = \{1, 8, 15\}$. L is again the Łukasiewicz algebra. The integral kernel $K : X \times Y \rightarrow L$ and a part of the integral kernel $Q : X \times X \rightarrow L$ are displayed in Table 3. We designed the shape of the integral kernel K to guarantee that K is Y -transitive.⁵ By Lemma 6.9, it suffices to verify whether the columns of K and Q coincide for $y_j = 1, 8, 15$. In Table 3, due to size constraints, we demonstrate this for the first two cases; however, the final case holds as well. Similarly to Example 6.2, fuzzy measures on $\langle X, \mathcal{P}(X) \rangle$ and $\langle Y, \mathcal{P}(Y) \rangle$ are determined as relative fuzzy measures $\mu_{\varphi_X}^r$ and $\mu_{\varphi_Y}^r$ modified by the functions $\varphi_X, \varphi_Y : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$, respectively. These functions are defined as follows:

$$\varphi_X(x) = \begin{cases} 6x, & x \leq \frac{2}{15}, \\ 0.8 + 0.75 \left(x - \frac{2}{15}\right), & \frac{2}{15} < x \leq \frac{6}{15}, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\varphi_Y(x) = \begin{cases} 2.4x, & x \leq \frac{1}{3}, \\ 0.8 + 0.6 \left(x - \frac{1}{3}\right), & \frac{1}{3} < x \leq \frac{2}{3}, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

⁵ The integral kernel K provides a fuzzy partition of X (see, Remark 4.1).

Table 3
The integral kernels K and a part of the integral kernel Q from Example 6.3.

x_i/y_j	1	8	15
1	1	0	0
2	1	0	0
3	1	0.8	0
4	1	0.9	0
5	0.9	1	0
6	0.8	1	0
7	0	1	0
8	0	1	0
9	0	1	0
10	0	1	0.8
11	0	1	0.9
12	0	0.9	1
13	0	0.8	1
14	0	0	1
15	0	0	1

(a) Integral kernel K

x_i/x_j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	1	1	0.2	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	1	0.2	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	1	1	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.2
4	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.2
5	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1	1	1	1	1	0.2
6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	1	1	1	1	0.2
7	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	1	1	1	0.2
8	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	1	1	1	0.2
9	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	1	1	1	0.2
10	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	1	1	1	1
11	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	1	1	1	1
12	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
13	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

(b) Integral kernel Q

Fig. 5. The approximations of an extensional function f (black) with respect to Q using compositions of lattice integral transforms from Example 6.3.

Table 4
Value of the Sugeno-like fuzzy integral of the square of Q for Cases 1 and 2 from Example 6.3.

Case/ x_i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	0.8	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.95	0.9	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.9	0.95	0.9	0.85	0.8	0.8
2	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8

It is evident that the fuzzy measure $\mu_X^1 = \mu_{\varphi_X}^r$, along with the kernel K , does not satisfy condition (C1). Similarly, the measure $\mu_Y^2 = \mu_{\varphi_Y}^r$ and the inverse kernel $K^{-1} = K^T$ also fail to meet this condition. The superscripts 1 and 2 are used to distinguish between the definitions of fuzzy measures corresponding to the compositions of lattice integral measures in (43) and (46), respectively. Henceforth, formula (43) will be referred to as Case 1, and formula (46) as Case 2. Additionally, we define $\mu_Y^1 = \mu_Y^1$ and $\mu_X^2 = \mu_X^1$ to ensure that the assumptions of the corresponding theorems regarding the satisfaction of condition (C2) are met. Finally, we consider an extensional function f on X with respect to Q , as shown in Fig. 5. It is straightforward to verify that this piecewise constant function, particularly, constant on the cores of the y -projections of the integral kernel K into X , is indeed extensional. Specifically, it suffices to construct a table containing the values $f(x_i) \leftrightarrow f(x_j)$ for all $x_i, x_j \in X$ and verify whether these values dominate the corresponding entries in the table for the integral kernel Q . The approximations of the extensional function f using the compositions of lattice integral transforms are displayed on Fig. 5. The values of the Sugeno-like fuzzy integrals of Q^2 in Cases 1 and 2 can be found in Table 4. It is easy to see that in both cases, the closeness between the approximate and the original function, measured by the biresiduum, at each point of X is greater than or equal to the value of the Sugeno-like fuzzy integral of the square of Q for the specific fuzzy measure, i.e., either $\mu_X^1 = \mu_{\varphi_X}^r$ or $\mu_Y^2 = \mu_{\varphi_Y}^r$. It is worth noting that integral kernels K with overlapping cores of their y -projections into X are often not Y -transitive. In such cases, applying a Y -transitivity process to Q , along with restricting Q to $X \times Y$, can help identify a Y -transitive integral kernel K . However, integral kernels constructed in this manner lose a certain sense of locality. Specifically, more distant points from X still exhibit a high degree of membership in the resulting integral kernel. A deeper analysis of the estimation of approximation quality will be the focus of our future research.

We have shown that the composition of lattice integral transforms preserves constant functions when conditions (C1) and (C2) are satisfied. A natural question arises: are constant functions the only ones preserved under these conditions? The following corollaries

demonstrate that the same conditions also guarantee the preservation of extensional functions with respect to Q , provided that (Q, μ_X) satisfies condition (C1) in one of the cases.

Corollary 6.12. *Let the assumptions of Theorem 6.10 be satisfied, and let (Q, μ_X) satisfy (C1). Then*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f) = f \tag{50}$$

for any extensional function f on X with respect to Q .

Proof. Obviously, if (Q, μ_X) satisfies (C1), then (Q^2, μ_X) satisfies (C1) as well. This immediately follows from $\text{Core}(Q_y) = \text{Core}(Q_y^2)$ for any $y \in X$. By Theorem 6.10, we simply find

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(f)(z) \leftrightarrow f(z) \geq \int_X^{\otimes} Q^2(x, z) d\mu_X = \int_X^{\otimes} \underline{\mathbb{1}}_X(x) \otimes Q^2(x, z) d\mu_X = F_{(Q^2, \mu_X)}^{\otimes}(\underline{\mathbb{1}}_X)(z) = \underline{\mathbb{1}}_Y(z) = \top,$$

where we used the preservation of constant functions. Hence, we get the desired equality as the consequence of the fact that $a \leftrightarrow b = \top$ if and only if $a = b$. \square

In the previous corollary, we have to assume that the condition (C1) is satisfied by (Q, μ_X) . By Lemma 6.9 and the assumption on Q , we have $Q(x, y) = K(x, y)$ for any $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$, which trivially gives: if (Q, μ_X) satisfies (C1), then (K, μ_X) satisfies (C1) as well. It is easy to see from Table 3(b) that the opposite implication is not true.

For the opposite composition of lattice integral transforms, the situation is simpler, as the integration of Q^2 is performed over Y for every $z \in X$ and (K^T, μ_Y) satisfies (C1) if and only if $(Q^T|_{Y \times X}, \mu_Y)$ satisfies (C1).

Corollary 6.13. *Let the assumption of Theorem 6.11 be satisfied such that Q is a Y -similarity on X , and let (K^{-1}, μ_Y) satisfy (C1). Then*

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f) = f \tag{51}$$

for any extensional function f on X with respect to Q .

Proof. Using Lemma 6.9, we have $Q^T(y, z) = K^{-1}(y, z)$ for any $z \in X$ and $y \in Y$. Since (K^{-1}, μ_Y) satisfies (C1), we trivially get that (Q^T, μ_Y) as well as $((Q^2)^T, \mu_Y)$ satisfies (C1). By Theorem 6.11, we find that

$$F_{(K^{-1}, \mu_Y)}^{\otimes} \circ F_{(K, \mu_X)}^{\rightarrow}(f)(z) \leftrightarrow f(z) \geq \int_Y^{\otimes} Q^2(z, y) d\mu_Y = \int_Y^{\otimes} \underline{\mathbb{1}}_Y(y) \otimes (Q^2)^T(y, z) d\mu_Y = F_{((Q^2)^T, \mu_Y)}^{\rightarrow}(\underline{\mathbb{1}}_Y)(z) = \underline{\mathbb{1}}_X(z) = \top,$$

where we used the preservation of constant functions. Hence, we get the desired equality as the consequence of the fact that $a \leftrightarrow b = \top$ if and only if $a = b$. \square

In Example 6.3, we introduced the fuzzy measures μ_X^1 and μ_Y^2 , which, along with K and K^T , respectively, did not satisfy condition (C1). The only way to ensure that (Q, μ_X^1) satisfies (C1) is to set $\mu_X^1 = \mu_X^{\top}$, and similarly, $\mu_Y^2 = \mu_Y^{\top}$ ensures that (K^T, μ_Y^2) satisfies (C1). Observe that the choice of the integral kernel K and, consequently, fuzzy measures results in the lattice integral transforms that are exactly lattice fuzzy transforms. A more in-depth analysis of integral kernels with overlapping cores of y -projections of K into X and their ability to preserve extensional functions will be the focus of our future research.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we investigated the approximation properties of lattice integral transforms, particularly their compositions, extending known results on lattice fuzzy transforms. We introduced the concept of a Q -inverse integral kernel and demonstrated its role in reconstructing lattice-valued functions. We showed that compositions of suitable lattice integral transforms provided upper and lower approximations of the original function transformed via the integral kernel Q . To assess approximation quality, we proposed a lattice-based modulus of continuity and showed that, under appropriate conditions on kernels and fuzzy measures, the closeness – measured via the biresiduum – between the original and reconstructed functions exceeded the value of modulus of continuity of the

original function. These results confirmed that approximation quality could be controlled by the parameters of the lattice integral transforms. Furthermore, under the assumption that $Y \subseteq X$ and that the Q -inverse kernel and a fuzzy measure on Y satisfied (C2), we showed that the approximation quality for extensional functions with respect to a Y -reflexive and Y -transitive kernel Q could be estimated via the integral of Q^2 . In certain cases, this led to exact reconstruction.

The presented results offer an insight into the performance of lattice version of integral transforms, nevertheless, one could see that certain constructions and conditions remain restrictive. For example, the modulus of continuity is based on an equivalence relation on X that disregards the membership degrees of K_y , or the integral kernel Q on X , determining inverse integral kernels, together with a fuzzy measure does not necessarily ensure preservation of constant functions, which leads to imprecise and potentially unusable upper or lower estimates (see, Fig. 3). These and other limitations motivate further investigation into the properties of integral kernels and fuzzy measures to refine the estimations of quality approximation, which would be valuable for practical applications. Beyond the refinement of these estimates, it is also worth noting that lattice integral transforms are constructed using operations from residuated lattices, which provide semantic interpretations for logical connectives such as conjunction and implication. Furthermore, the Sugeno integral has been generalized within logical frameworks (see, e.g., [6,10]). Consequently, exploring a logical formalization for these integral transforms could offer a novel and potentially powerful perspective on their behavior and applicability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Viec Bui Quoc: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Michal Holčapek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the editor and anonymous referees for their valuable comments and constructive suggestions that significantly helped us to improve the paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] M. Baaz, Infinite-valued Gödel logic with 0-1-projections and relativizations, in: *Gödel'96: Logical Foundations of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics*, in: *Lecture Notes in Logic*, vol. 6, Springer-Verlag, 1996, pp. 23–33.
- [2] M. Baczyński, B. Jayaram, *Fuzzy Implications*, Springer, Heidelberg, 2010.
- [3] B. Bede, I.J. Rudas, Approximation properties of fuzzy transforms, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 180 (1) (2011) 20–40.
- [4] R. Bělohlávek, *Fuzzy Relational Systems: Foundations and Principles*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, New York, 2002.
- [5] L. Debnath, D. Bhatta, *Integral Transforms and Their Applications*, CRC Press, New York, 1914.
- [6] P. Dellunde, L. Godo, E. Marchioni, On the logical formalization of possibilistic counterparts of states over n -valued Lukasiewicz events, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 52 (1) (2011) 63–75.
- [7] D. Dubois, H. Prade, A. Rico, Residuated variants of Sugeno integrals: towards new weighting schemes for qualitative aggregation methods, *Inf. Sci.* 329 (2016) 765–781.
- [8] A. Dvořák, M. Holčapek, L -fuzzy quantifiers of type $\langle 1 \rangle$ determined by fuzzy measures, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 160 (23) (2009) 3425–3452.
- [9] A. Dvořák, M. Holčapek, Fuzzy measures and integrals defined on algebras of fuzzy subsets over complete residuated lattices, *Inf. Sci.* 185 (1) (2012) 205–229.
- [10] T. Flaminio, L. Godo, E. Marchioni, On the logical formalization of possibilistic counterparts of states over n -valued Lukasiewicz events, *J. Log. Comput.* 21 (3) (2011) 429–446.
- [11] N. Galatos, P. Jipsen, T. Kowalski, H. Ono, *Residuated Lattices: An Algebraic Glimpse at Substructural Logics*, *Studies in Logic and Foundations of Mathematics*, vol. 151, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2007.
- [12] P. Hájek, *Metamathematics of Fuzzy Logic*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1998.
- [13] M. Holčapek, T. Tichý, Discrete fuzzy transform of higher degree, in: *2014 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE)*, 2014, pp. 604–611.
- [14] M. Holčapek, Q.B. Vec, On an application of lattice-valued integral transform to multicriteria decision making, in: *Soft Computing: Biomedical and Related Applications*, Springer, 2021, pp. 137–149.
- [15] M. Holčapek, Q.B. Vec, P. Ferbas, On an application of lattice integral transforms in image processing, *Mathematics* 10 (21) (2022) 4077.
- [16] M. Holčapek, B. Vec, On integral transforms for residuated lattice-valued functions, in: *Proc. of Information Processing Management of Uncertainty (IPMU) 2020*, IPMU, 2020, pp. 1–14.
- [17] M. Holčapek, Q.B. Vec, Integral transforms on spaces of complete residuated lattice valued functions, in: *Proc. of IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence (WCCI) 2020*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [18] M. Holčapek, Q.B. Vec, Reconstruction of lattice-valued functions by integral transforms, in: *International Workshop on Fuzzy Logic and Applications (WILF) 2021*, WILF, 2021, pp. 1–8.
- [19] E.P. Klement, R. Mesiar, E. Pap, *Triangular Norms*, *Trends in Logic*, vol. 8, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 2000.
- [20] G.J. Klir, B. Yuan, *Fuzzy Sets and Fuzzy Logic: Theory and Applications*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1995.
- [21] J. Močkoř, Spaces with fuzzy partitions and fuzzy transform, *Soft Comput.* 21 (13) (2017) 3479–3492.

- [22] J. Močkoř, Axiomatic of lattice-valued F-transform, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 342 (2018) 53–66.
- [23] J. Močkoř, F-transforms and semimodule homomorphisms, *Soft Comput.* 23 (2019) 7603–7619.
- [24] J. Močkoř, M. Holčapek, Fuzzy objects in spaces with fuzzy partitions, *Soft Comput.* 21 (24) (2017) 726–7284.
- [25] J. Močkoř, P. Hurtík, Lattice-valued F-transforms and similarity relations, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 342 (2018) 67–89.
- [26] V. Novák, I. Perfilieva, J. Močkoř, *Mathematical Principles of Fuzzy Logic*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Boston, 1999.
- [27] I. Perfilieva, Fuzzy transforms: theory and applications, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 157 (8) (2006) 993–1023.
- [28] I. Perfilieva, S.P. Tiwari, A.P. Singh, Lattice-valued F-transforms as interior operators of L-fuzzy pretopological spaces, in: J. Medina, et al. (Eds.), *Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems, Theory and Foundations, IPMU 2018*, in: *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 854, 2018, pp. 163–174.
- [29] Z. Shokrollah, I. Perfilieva, On the approximation properties of fuzzy transform, *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* 33 (1) (2017) 171–180.
- [30] M. Sugeno, *Theory of Fuzzy Integrals and its Applications*, PhD thesis, Tokyo Institute of Technology, 1974.
- [31] P. Sussner, Lattice fuzzy transforms from the perspective of mathematical morphology, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 288 (2016) 115–128.
- [32] F.C. Tenoudji, *Analog and Digital Signal Analysis: From Basics to Applications*, Springer, Switzerland, 2016.
- [33] S.P. Tiwari, I. Perfilieva, A.P. Singh, Generalized residuated lattices based F-transform, *Iran. J. Fuzzy Syst.* 18 (2) (2015) 165–182.
- [34] Z. Wang, G.J. Klir, *Fuzzy Measure Theory*, Plenum Press, New York, 1992.
- [35] Z. Wang, G.J. Klir, *Generalized Measure Theory*, vol. XV, *IFSR International Series on Systems Science and Engineering*, vol. 25, Springer, New York, NY, 2009, p. 381.
- [36] A.M. Yaglom, *An Introduction to the Theory of Stationary Random Functions*, vol. XIII, revised English ed., translated and edited by Richard A. Silverman, Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1962, p. 235.